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*Lahita R, Kluger J, Drayer DE, Koffler D, Reidenberg MM. Antibodies to nuclear antigens in patients treated with procainamide or acetylprocainamide. *N Engl J Med* 1979; 301:1382-5.

Book, personal author(s)

Ringsven MK, Bond D. Gerontology and leadership skills for nurses. 2nd ed. Albany (NY): Delmar Publishers; 1996, pp 30-45.

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Patient perception of the support initiative of perioperative care

Jalina Karim, Aini Ahmad, Azhar Mahmud Merican, Mohd Hasni Ju'afar

Abstract

Background: The purpose of this study was to determine the relationship between demographic factors and the support initiative on the delivering of perioperative care in the operation theatre.

Patients and Methods: This study was a quantitative descriptive cross sectional study. The study was carried out in one of the public university hospital which involved the Surgical, Urology, Orthopedic, Ophthalmology, Otorhinolaryngology, Obstetrics and Gynaecology post operative patients between December 2008 and February 2009. The instrument used was a questionnaires that related to the perioperative experience for the patients to rate the perioperative care that they received. It consists of close ended and open ended questions. The obtained data were analyzed and the results were tabulated.

Results: Results indicated that only 38(6.9%) of the patients satisfied that they were able to influence the treatment and only 34 (22.8%) of them satisfied with the chances given to them to listen to music during the delivery of perioperative care. Patients also gave suggestion in the open ended section to propose the music in the operation theatre.

Conclusion: The result of the study gave the opportunity for the staff to be more supportive and attentive to the patients during their perioperative care.

The N Iraqi J Med, April 2011; 8(1):5-8

Keywords: Music therapy, perioperative, perioperative care, perioperative nursing

INTRODUCTION

Health care industry has undergone vast improvements and changes in these recent years. In order to enhance a good quality services, it is an essential to improve a health care system. Many organizations are focusing on improving the quality of nursing services in order to obtain patient satisfaction. Good quality of health care should enhance patient's satisfaction in their services. Therefore, to ensure a good quality of health care, patients should have an easy access to services, they have a decision, welfare, privacy, self esteem, ease, continuity of services and belief.

The operating department is a dynamic and challenging area to work and thus the perioperative nursing is a complex arena that involves various roles and procedures⁽¹⁾. In order to achieve the quality of perioperative care, there is a need to regularly carry out beneficial interventions, attain quality outcome and be attentive to the patient⁽²⁾. According to perioperative nurses who tried their best to support a positive environment will enhance a supportive experience for patients^(3, 4). Perioperative nurses have a responsibility to deliver a holistic care of surgical patients^[4]. All patients are unique because they have their own feelings and thinking when they arrived in operation theatre and must be treated as an individual⁽⁵⁾. Often patient feels less of control and autonomy when they were scheduled for surgery⁽⁶⁾. Patient satisfaction can be viewed as complicated concept because it involves the psychological, physiological and even sociology aspect. It is

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determined by the quality care given and the patient expectations about the care provided (7, 21). Patient viewed their perioperative experience as good when they want to be painless, nausea free, and de-stress; they want to have some authority over their care and recovery progresses smoothly (3).

The concept of this study was based on the "Good Nursing Care" theoretical framework that has been modified by (8). One of the elements in the "Good Nursing Care" is supporting initiative which consists of the following elements: - such as encouragement to participate in care, chance to influence, chance to listen to music.

The American Music Therapy Association (1999) interprets the music therapy as an accepted health professions whereby it has a beneficial correlation to the physiological, psychological and social requires of an individual (9). Music intervention support the psychological needs by maintain the relaxation and enhance the patient well being and comfort (10).

Considering the above facts, the present study was conducted to determine the relationship between demographic factors and the support initiative. We conducted this study for the reason that it will be beneficial for the future clinical nursing practice, nursing research and also nursing education.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

This quantitative descriptive cross sectional study aimed to expose the experience of 183 patients who underwent surgery. In Malaysia, we have multi ethnic groups, therefore, the patients in this study comprised of Malays, Chinese, Indians or others. Postoperative patients from general Surgery, Urology, Orthopaedic, Ophtalmology, Otorhinolaryngology, and Obstetrics and Gynaecology were invited to take part in the study. The questionnaire was given to the patients on the first day or third postoperative day for that post Patient Controlled Analgesia (PCA). The questionnaire by Leinonen et al (2001) was adopted with partial modification. The questionnaire had three section; section A- operation background which had to be filled up by the researcher according to the patients' case notes, section B- demographic data and preoperative phase and section C concerning the perioperative care from patients' perception. The section C consisted of two types of questions; close and open ended questions. The structural validity of the instrument were tested by the panel expert of opinion and the reliability checked by using Cronbach's alpha was 0.934.

Patients who went for more than one type of surgery were excluded because of the level of pain were different. The sample consisted of men and women ranging between 19 to 75 years of age, of whom

62.9% were first time undergoing operation. This study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the teaching hospital. To maintain the confidentiality, each respondent was given a number which was the only identification used on the questionnaire that related to this study.

RESULTS

Through a questionnaire, a total of 183 individuals responded for this study. Male patients were more unsatisfied 39 (83%) on the supporting initiative than female 77 (71.3%) (Table.1). Satisfaction was higher among the female 31 (28.7%) and only 8 (17%) of the male patients reported to be satisfied.

The analysis according to ethnicity showed that non Malays patients 41 (80.4%) were more unsatisfied on the supporting patient as compared to Malays patients 75 (72.1%). Seventy one (71) of those who were in low education patients were more unsatisfied than the high education 45 (70.3%). Satisfaction was higher among the high education group 19 (29.7%) and only 20 (22%) of the low education group were satisfied.

Those patients who were unemployed 43 (83.3%) were unsatisfied with the supporting patient and this percentage was higher as compared to employed 71 (70.3%).

Satisfaction was higher among the employed patients 30 (29.7%) and only 9 (16.7%) unemployed patients were satisfied.

Analysis according to the status showed that 90 (75%) married patients were more unsatisfied on the supporting patient. Only 30 (25%) of the married patients felt satisfied. For those patients who were currently single, 26 (74.3%) of them claimed that they were unsatisfied and only 9 (25.7%) of them were satisfied.

Results showed that there was no relationship of the patient's perceptions on the supporting patient and the demographic factors. Statistical test has shown that there were no statistical significant differences between the perceptions of patients on supporting patient and on the demographic factors with a P value > 0.05.

	Patient perceptions on supporting patient		χ^2	p-value	
	Satisfied	Unsatisfied			
Gender					
	Female	31 (28.7)	77 (71.3)	2.37	0.123
	Male	8 (17.0)	39 (83.0)		
Ethnicity				1.25	0.265
	Malays	29 (27.9)	75 (72.1)		
	Non-Malays	10 (19.6)	41 (80.4)		
Level of education				1.18	0.276
	Low	20 (22.0)	71 (78.0)		
	High	19 (29.7)	45 (70.3)		
Occupation status				3.18	0.075
	Employed	30 (29.7)	71 (70.3)		
	Unemployed	9 (16.7)	45 (83.3)		
Marital status				0.01	0.932
	Currently single	9 (25.7)	26 (74.3)		
	Married	30 (25.0)	90 (75.0)		

Table 1: The relationship of the patient's perception on the supporting patients and the demographic factors

DISCUSSION

As a healthcare professional, we come into contact and give support to the patients during perioperative care. In this study, the patients gave low ratings of satisfaction to supporting initiative. Commonly patient used to choose the surgeon themselves but not the anaesthetist (20). Patients should be increasingly involved in decision making concerning their treatment and this resulting better outcomes (11, 12). Researchers found that patient should be encouraged to ask when they are not clear on what happening to them and help them to achieve self esteem (11). The feeling of fear with pain that caused by the anaesthesia (20); frightened of waking up during procedure or dying (13) and operation were high among the patients during arrival compared to when they left the department. Findings from (14), anaesthesia and possible difficulty with the surgery were the most commonly patients expressed fears. However, patients did not realize the importance of the anaesthetist along the surgery (20). The findings of this study are similar to earlier findings whereby the non Malays were more satisfied with the care given as compared to the Malays patients but the results were not statistically significant (21). This is most probably because of the total number of non Malay participated in this study was less as compared to Malays patients.

The use of music and humorous distractions has been the focus of several pieces of research. In this study, the satisfaction among the respondents on the chance to listen to music was low and this was similar to earlier research findings (15). Other researchers found that music is a positive intervention, and improves

patient comfort and satisfaction (6, 10, 14, 16, 17, 18). Music can touch patient deeply, transforming their anxiety and stress into relaxation and healing and reduce the use of sedatives and analgesics (10). Music used during surgical experience might induce relaxation by having rhythm and tempo slightly lower than normal rate of heart beat (10). The need of the music also was supported by the suggestion from the patients in this study that they needed the music to reduce their anxiety. Few studies showed a significant reduction in anxiety level when the patient is being exposed to the music during perioperative time (19). Therefore, there is evidence that music should be introduced as an innovation to the perioperative area and it acts as a relaxation therapy for the patients to overcome their feeling.

This study highlighted the concept of the perioperative care given to patients. The nurse educators may also integrate caring concepts for the perioperative patient into the nursing curriculum development by adopting the 'Good Nursing Care' framework.

CONCLUSION

This research study has important implications for the future clinical nursing practice, research and education because the perioperative care gives an impact on the patient satisfaction. It is an important to provide information based on the evidence in the perioperative area to the nurse manager and nurses. The research findings clearly indicated that support initiative appeared to be a needful for the perioperative patients. In addition, some patients gave opinion to have music in operation theatre in order to help them to allay their

anxiety level. Therefore, it is good to introduce an innovation such as music in the perioperative area because it is reasonable and simple. It is an important to meet the patient needs because it will help to reduce the patients' anxiety and discomfort in the perioperative area.

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The outcome in upper gastrointestinal bleeding

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Abstract

Background and Objectives: The upper gastrointestinal bleeding (UGIB) is one of the most important emergency cases that remain the common cause of emergency hospitalization and death occurrence.

The aim of this study is to determine the underlying causes of upper GI bleeding in AL-Kadhmiya teaching hospital and factors influence the outcome results in regards to emergency surgery; spontaneous resolution episodes & mortality incidence.

Methods: This is a prospective study of (75) patients presented with upper gastrointestinal bleeding (UGIB) for 18 months from June 2008 to November 2009. All patients underwent endoscopy during the first (48) hours of admission.

Results: The patient's age group is between 15-80 years. The male patients 58(77.3%) the female patients 17(22.6%). Duodenal ulcer was the commonest causes of UGIB 35patients (46.6%) followed by esophageal varices 18patients (24%) then gastric erosion 13patients (17.3%) then GA-stomach 4patients (5.3%) then esophageal erosion 3patients (4%) then gastric ulcer 1patients (1.3%).

Sixty patients (80%) of those patients responded to conservative treatment while 15 patients (20%) required surgical treatment, as emergency operation in 10 patients (13.3%) or elective operation in 5 patients (6.66%).

The highest mortality rate was found patients with hypotension 9 patients (12%) then in those patients with age more than 50 years 6 patients (8%).

Conclusions: The commonest cause of UGIB in AL-Kadhmiya teaching hospital is chronic duodenal ulcer.

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Keywords: Upper gastrointestinal bleeding, endoscopy

INTRODUCTION

Acute upper gastrointestinal bleeding (UGIB) is a potentially life threatening abdominal emergency that remains the common cause of hospitalization. Upper GI bleeding is defined as bleeding derived from a source proximal to ligament of treitz. Bleeding from the upper GI tract is a proximately 4 times as common as bleeding from the lower GI tract and is a major cause of morbidity and mortality. mortality rates from the UGIB are 6-10% overall [1-4]. A history of recent non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drug (NSAID) abuse should elicit concern about bleeding from a peptic ulcer [3,4]. UGI

bleeding can be classified into several broad categories based upon anatomic and path physiologic factors. several endoscopic studies have described the most common causes [5,6,7]

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Seventy five patients were randomly collected from different departments in AL-Kadhmiya teaching hospital suffering from UGIB for the period between June 2008 till November 2009, and data from these patients were analyzed to study causes and effects of different parameters on the outcome of those patients UGIB presented with either

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hematemesis or melena or both or sometime fresh blood per rectum.

Hematemesis was defined as vomiting of blood clot or coffee ground material. Melena was defined as the passage of black tarry stool. After initial resuscitation, and bearing in mind that endoscopic diagnosis falls rapidly after 24 hours as small lesions may heal or develop after initial bleeding. Most of the endoscopies were done during the first 24 hours of the admission.

Endoscopy: Upper GIT endoscopy was carried out within 48 hours of admission. premeditation used consist of local xylocain spray 2% and metochloperamide was titrated intravenously with difficult endoscopy.

The site of bleeding was documented by visualization of any one or combination of:-

- 1-An actively bleeding lesion.
- 2-A fresh or altered blood clot or black slough adherent to a lesion.
- 3- A vessel protruding from the margin of an ulcer.

Gastric erosion was identified underlying cause of bleeding if sever erythema with or without erosion was actively bleeding or there was a clot in base of one or more of erosions.

Outcome Assessment:

Outcome was assessed in respect of:

(a) Mortality within the period of admission (range=7-21 days).

(b)Emergency surgery defined as an operation performed in the case of homodynamic instability or no response to medical treatment.

(c) Spontaneous arrest of bleeding by conservative management and without emergency surgery or death within 30 days of bleeding episode. The following risk factors at presentation were analyzed in relation to outcome:

- ° Age
- ° Transfusion requirement
- ° Aspirin or other NSAID ingestion: Aspirin or NSAID intake was defined as ingestion of any of these compounds prior to and within a week of the onset of symptoms.
- ° Presence of complicating concomitant disease
- ° Underlying chronic liver function test & previous history of such diseases.
- ° Active bleeding at time of endoscopy.

° Concomitant diseases are ischemic heart disease, hypertension, diabetes mellitus, burn, bleeding disorders (hemophilia, thalassaemia), and congestive heart failure.

RESULTS

Seventy five patients 58 males (77.3%):17 females (22.6%) with mean age 47.5 of years (range 15 to 80 years) with UGIB were studied randomly. Twenty three patients (30.6%) presented with hematemesis,

13 patients presented with melena and 39 patients (52%) with both. (table1).

presentation	No. of patients	%
hematemesis	23	30.6
Melena	13	17.3
Both	39	52
Total	75	100

Table 1: Patient presentation:

Bleeding sites:

Duodenal ulcer was the most common source of bleeding 35 patients (46.6%),Esophageal varices 18 patients (24%) ,gastric erosion 13 patients (17.3%) ,CA of stomach 4 patients (5.3%) ,esophageal erosion 3 patients (4%) ,gastric ulcer 1 patients (1.3%) ,fundal varices 1 patients (1.3%).table 2.

Bleeding site	No. of patients	%	Males	Females
D.U	35	46.6	31	4
Esophageal varices	18	24	13	5
Gastric erosions	13	17.3	10	3
Ca stomach	4	5.33	1	3
Esophageal erosion	3	4	2	1
G.U.	1	1.3	1	
Fundal varices	1	1.3		1
Total	75	100	58	17
			77.3%	22.6%

Table 2: Bleeding sites of UGIB

Previous attack of bleeding

A history of previous UGIB was elicited in 32 patients (42.6%) most frequently in patients with D.U. 17 patients (22.6%), then esophageal varices 11 patients (14.6%), CA stomach 2 patients (2.6%), gastric erosion 1 patients (1.3%), and fundal varices 1 (1.3%).

Age: The youngest patients were 15 years; the oldest age was 80 years, mean age 47.5 years.

Number of patients above 50 years is (19) 6 of them were dead with mortality rate of 8%.

Figure-1: Age in Year Age distribution in UGIB

Blood pressure on admission: Hypotension was associated with highest mortality rate. 32 patients presented with systolic blood pressure less than 100 mmHg, 12% of them died.

NSAID ingestion: Sixteen patients (21.3%) with UGIB gave history of NSAID intake within one week of attack. 9 patients (12%) with gastric erosion. 6 patients (8%) with D.U. 1 patients (1.3%) with esophageal varices.

Concomitant disease : Concomitant disease was found in 18 patients (24%). sixteen patients (21.33%) were responding to conservative treatment. two patients (2.66%) required emergency operation of all patient with concomitant disease 4 patients (5.33%) were died.

Liver disease: Fifteen patients (20%) had underlying liver disease. 14 patients (18.66%) managed conservatively and 1 patient (1.3%) managed surgically. Mortality rate was 5 patients (6.66%).

Active bleeding: Fifteen

patients (20%) had active bleeding on endoscopy. 10 patients (13.33%) responded to conservative treatment. 4 patients (5.33%) required surgical treatment. of all 3 patients (4%) died.

Transfusion requirement

19 patients (25.3%) required blood transfusion of more than 6 units on admission. 8 patients (10.66%) required surgical treatment. Of all 5 patients (6.66%) died.

Outcome

Sixty patients (80%) had spontaneous arrest on conservative treatment 15 patients (20%) required surgical treatment.

Ten patients (13.3%) were managed by emergency operation,

5 patients (6.6%) by elective operation. Recurrent bleeding occurred in 8 patients (10.6%), of those 5 patients (6.66%) died. Of those treated conservatively, 7 patients (9.3%) died because of re-bleeding within a month of admission.

Of those treated by emergency operation, 3 patients (4%) died.

None of those treated by elective operation died.

Mortality rate: In general mortality rate of the study was 10 patients (13.3%) [table3]. The highest mortality rate was among those patients with hypotension on admission. (9 patients died with mortality rate 12%). In patients with age above 50 years, the mortality rate was 6 patients (8%).

In those patients with chronic liver disease & those with transfusion requirement more than 6 unit of blood, number of died were 5 patients (6.66%) for each. The same mortality rate was found among those with re-bleeding (5 patients, 6.66%).

In those patients with concomitant disease, 4 patients (5.33%) were died.

Discussion

This study shows that the main age group affected by UGIB was (40-50) years with mean age of 47.5 years. This result concedes with that of Mohammed At. Etal⁽⁸⁾ in which the main age group was affected by UGIB was (40-50) years. However; other studies found the main age group affected is (50-60) years^(6,7).

The male to female ratio in this study were 3.4:1. The result was in accordance with previous reports^(6,8).

This study shows that the chronic duodenal ulcer was the commonest cause of UGIB in 35 patients (46.6%). then esophageal varices 18 patients (24%) then gastric erosion 13 patients (17.3%) this results concedes with Javad salimi etal⁽⁹⁾ in which the duodenal ulcer was the most com cause of UGIB 38% and Leonardo⁽¹⁰⁾ Tammar etal 33% but the percentage lower than in our study. the result in accordance with Fa.zaA Qari etal⁽¹¹⁾ in which the esophageal varices the most common cause of UGIB 57% then duodenal ulcer 20%.

This study shows that the over all mortality was 13.3%. this result concedes with that of Javad Salimi etal in which the mortality rate was 13.9% but the result in accordance with Fallah MA etal⁽¹⁾ the mortality rate 6-10%.

In this study the Marjory of 60 patient (80%) respond to conservative treatment while 15 patients (20%) required surgical intervention to stop bleeding this result concede with that of Fallah MA etal⁽¹⁾ in which 80% respond to conservative medical treatment.

In our study low blood pressure on admission associated with highest mortality rate.

In our study the mortality rate is increased with advancing age particularly for patients above 50 years. This suggests that surgery could be delayed until there is spontaneous resolution of bleeding without risk at an earlier stage of bleeding.

Concomitant disease as diabetes mellitus and chronic liver disease was important risk factors of mortality and both of them might be an important factor in high mortality rate seen in patients with bleeding from esophageal varices.

Blood transfusion requirement of more than 6 pints is associated with increased mortality rate and it may reflect continued bleeding.

Re-bleeding was associated with the high mortality rate in this study. On endoscopy stigmata of bleeding is associated with high mortality rate (20%).

Conclusion

The commonest cause of UGIB in Al - Kadhmiya hospital is chronic D.U. followed by esophageal varices. High risk group with UGIB which require early surgical intervention are patients over 50 years of age and those with re-bleeding, hypotension on admission, blood transfusion more than 6 unit, active bleeding on endoscopy and those with chronic liver disease.

Recommendation

Early surgical treatment after stabilization of condition, and on the same admission is advised.

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Scleroderma diabeticorum and waxy skin syndrome among diabetics and the non- diabetics of Punjab

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Abstract

Diabetes mellitus is a common condition which frequently has skin manifestations. The attachment of glucose to protein may result in a profound effect on structure and function of that protein, and account for clinical manifestations of the disease. It has been suggested that increased cross linking of collagen in diabetic patients is responsible for the fact that their skin is generally thicker than that of non-diabetics. The present study was undertaken to assess the incidence and to compare the incidence of waxy skin and scleroderma in diabetics and non diabetics. The study was done on 250 patients who attended the Skin OPD of Guru Nanak Dev Hospital, Amritsar. Thorough general physical examination and the dermatological examination were done in each case. All the cases of scleroderma and waxy skin were noted and compared between diabetics and non diabetic patients.

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Keywords: Scleroderma, cutaneous manifestations, diabetic complications, collagen disorders.

INTRODUCTION

The cutaneous involvement of diabetes mellitus is indeed protean. Nearly one third of diabetic patients have cutaneous manifestations. [1] A broad spectrum of cutaneous disorders may be encountered in patients with both type I and type 2

diabetes mellitus. On occasion, these dermatologic findings may precede any clinical or biochemical evidence for diabetes. An estimated 30% of patients with diabetes develop skin manifestations during the course of their chronic illness. Although the mechanism for much diabetes associated skin conditions remains unknown, the pathogenesis of others is linked to abnormal carbohydrate metabolism. [2] Several skin conditions are specific to diabetes, but most of them also occur in the non-diabetic population. [3]

It was concluded by Mackool et al [4] that the amount of glucose in whole skin is greater than can be attributed to distribution in extracellular fluid. The

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ratio of glucose/gm skin to glucose /gm blood is increased in diabetic skin, suggesting that the insulin regulates intracellular deposition of glucose in the skin. According to Freinkel and Freinkel [5] who studied 100 hospital based patients with diabetes mellitus, 14% had Scleroedema Diabeticorum. He also concluded that the duration of Scleroedema also correlated with the duration of diabetes. These findings highlight the relatively common occurrence of this skin condition which goes often unrecognised in people with diabetes.

Thickening of skin of the hand is a common occurrence, with a range of manifestation from simple pebbling of the knuckles to the diabetic hand syndrome. The diabetic hand syndrome consists of thickened skin over the dorsum of the digits and limited joint mobility, especially of the interphalangeal joints. [6][7][8]

The diabetic hand syndrome consists of thickened skin over the dorsum of the digits and limited joint mobility, especially of interphalangeal joints. The earliest description of this phenomenon was apparently the observation that insulin dependent diabetes was occasionally complicated by painful stiff hands. [9] At least 30% of diabetic patients have hand skin thickening, and some have demonstrable involvement of the dorsum of the feet. Clinical clues which suggest such a thickening include difficulty in tenting the skin, pebbled or rough skin on the knuckles or periungual region [6] and decreased skin wrinkling following immersion in water. [10] Biopsy specimens of involved skin show pronounced thickening of periarticular rather than articular collagen, which may be due to non-enzymatic glycosylation of collagen.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

In this study 250 patients were evaluated in the Department of Skin and STD OPD, Govt. Medical College, Guru Nanak Dev Hospital, Amritsar. The patients were equally divided into two groups of 125 patients each (Group A and Group B). Group A: consisted of 125 diabetics in the age group of 30-60 years taken from Skin and STD OPD. Group B: consisted of 125 non-diabetic control patients taken randomly from Skin and STD OPD in the age group of 30-60 years. The diabetics were diagnosed as per the revised criteria of glucose tolerance given by Alvin (2001). [11] Routine investigations were done in each case in both the groups. Certain special investigations to confirm the diagnosis were carried out where required. Fundoscopic examination was done. The incidence of scleroderma diabeticorum and waxy skin in diabetic group, non-diabetic control group were assessed separately and then the incidence of scleroderma and waxy skin were compared in the two groups to know whether diabetes mellitus had any association with diseases of skin.

RESULTS

The incidence of waxy skin was 41 (32.8%) cases in diabetic group and 25 (20%) cases in non-diabetic group. The difference was statistically significant. The incidence of scleroderma diabeticorum was 1 (0.8%) cases each in diabetic group and 0% in non-diabetic group and in all the above conditions the difference was statistically non-significant. (Table I and Table II)

Groups	Total	Cases of waxy skin	%age	Cases Scleroderma diabeticorum	of %age	%age
Diabetics A	125	41	32.8	1	0.8	44.8
Non-Diabetics B	125	25	20.0	0	0.0	40.0

TABLE I : INCIDENCE OF SCLERODERMA DIABETICORUM AND WAXY SKIN OBSERVED AMONG DIABETIC AND NON-DIABETICS

Manifestation	Group A(Diabetic) n=125		Group B(Non-Diabetic)n=125		X ²	p value
	No	%	No	%		
WAXY SKIN	41	32.8	25	20.0	4.24	<0.05
SCLERODERMA DIABETICORUM	1	0.8	0	0	0.80	>0.05

TABLE II: COMPARATIVE PATTERN OF SCLERODERMA DIABETICORUM AND WAXY SKIN GROUP A AND GROUP B

Weight status	No. of cases	%age
Under weight	14	11.2
Healthy	43	34.4
Overweight	41	32.8
Obese	24	19.2
Very obese	3	2.4
Total	125	100

TABLE III: THE OBESITY STATUS OF DIABETIC CASES

Age group (in years)	No. of cases	%age
30- 40	26	20.8
>40-50	43	34.4
>50- 60	56	44.8
Total	125	100

TABLE IV: AGE WISE DISTRIBUTION OF DIABETIC CASES

Sex	No. of Cases	%age
Female	83	66.4
Male	42	36.0
Total	125	100

TABLE V : SEX WISE DISTRIBUTION OF DIABETIC CASES

DISCUSSION

Persons with diabetes tend to have thicker skin than their non-diabetic counterparts. There are three aspects to this observation. Firstly, diabetics in general have a clinically inapparent but measurable increase in skin thickness unassociated with symptoms and which go unnoticed by

patients and physicians. Using pulsed ultrasound, it can be demonstrated that diabetics have thicker forearm skin than their age and sex matched non diabetic counterparts. [12] Second is clinically apparent thickening of skin involving the fingers and hands ranging from pebbled skin of knuckles to diabetic hand syndrome. The diabetic hand syndrome (Waxy skin) consists of thickened skin over the dorsum of digits and limited joint mobility, especially of the interphalangeal joints. [13] Third is an infrequent syndrome of diabetic scleroedema in which the patient develops markedly thickened dennis on the upper back. Thickening of the skin on the backs of the hands may occur in as many as 20% to 30% of persons with diabetes. [14]

Scleroedema adulatorum

Scleroedema adulatorum of diabetes is a syndrome characterized by a marked increase in dermal thickness posteriorly on back and upper neck in middle aged, overweight, poorly controlled type II diabetic subjects. It is not recognised as being related to digital sclerosis and we found no correlation by ultrasound measurements of back skin and hand skin thickness. It has a reported prevalence of 2.5% in patients with type II diabetes. [15]

Histologically one finds a thickened dermis with large collagen bundles that are separated by wide, clear spaces. There may be increased number of mast cells. [16] Scleroedema adulatorum a well-defined entity has been recognised a cutaneous manifestation of diabetes. In contrast to the identical changes occurring after infection scleroedema associated with diabetes may not remit even after long periods of time. Diabetic scleroedema occurs mainly in obese diabetic individuals with evidence of vascular complications. [17]

An excellent review of literature [18] also concluded that Scleroedema Diabeticorum is a diffuse, nonpitting induration of the skin characteristically occurring on the upper back, neck and shoulders in 2.5% of diabetics resulting in the limitation of movement. [19] [4] It has also suggested,

A) Scleroedema of Buschke, which occurs at any age and undergoes spontaneous resolution in 8-18 months.

B) Scleroedema diutinum, which does not follow acute infection, tends to chronicity and is often associated with diabetes mellitus [15] Male diabetics are more affected than female (ratio 4: 1). Generally the diabetes is long standing and patients are obese, exhibiting high frequency of Diabetic Retinopathy, neuropathy, hypertension and Ischemic heart disease. [3]

The incidence of limited joint mobility ranged from 8-50%. The variations of incidence are probably explainable by differences in age groups, duration of diabetes in the studies and lack of standardized testing.

Rosenbloom and Fraix described three adolescent patients with the syndrome of long-standing diabetes mellitus, restricted joint mobility, thick tight waxy skin, growth impairment, and maturational delay. Rosenbloom et al later reported in a study of 309 mostly juvenile diabetics that 30 percent had joint limitation and one third of these had thick tight, waxy skin that the examiner could not tent, mostly involving the dorsum of the hands. This work has been confirmed by other authors and these observations have been extended to patients with type II diabetes mellitus. [7]

The skin becomes thickened, with a waxy appearance, in about one third of patients. Such a skin resembles sclerodermic skin; however, the absence of other signs (Raynaud's phenomenon, ulcerations, nail calcinosis, and visceral organ involvement) clearly rules systemic scleroderma out. Histologically, dermal collagen thickening and elastic fiber reduction are observed. [20] The presence of diabetes mellitus is generally associated with measurably thickened skin. Using pulsed ultrasound, it can be demonstrated that diabetics have thicker forearm skin than their age and sex-matched non-diabetic counterparts. Contrary to the pattern in non-diabetics, skin thickness may increase with age (apparently associated with increased duration of diabetes.) Most studies have used the upper extremity skin in evaluating skin thickness, and it may not be a valid conclusion that diabetic skin is thickened at other sites.

Some researchers have also demonstrated an increased skin thickness on the dorsum of the feet, but not the back, suggesting that increased skin thickness is not necessarily universal in diabetes. It appears to be a safe observation that patients with diabetes mellitus have thicker skin on their

extremities. These terms are synonyms denoting one and the same skin disorder.

In European literature, the term scleroderma-like syndrome (SLS) is preferred, whereas the terms reduced joint mobility and waxy skin syndrome prevail in American literature.^[20]

To evaluate the frequency of SLS and its association with other diabetes-related pathology in diabetic population among Jewish and Arab patients, 153 IDDM patients and 45 healthy age- and gender-matched controls were studied. While no diabetes-related pathology was found in the controls, SLS was detected in 47% of all patients (skin, 31.4%; arthropathy, 37.9%; both, 22%). Independent of age, SLS directly correlated with diabetes duration ($p < 0.01$). One or more features of systemic diabetic involvement were present in 22% of patients with SLS, compared to only 7.2% in patients without SLS ($p < 0.009$). When patients were analyzed according to ethnicity, the frequency of skin involvement and neuropathy were found to be higher among Arab patients, particularly males ($p < 0.002$ and $p < 0.005$, respectively), and detection of one was significantly associated with the presence of the other ($p < 0.001$). In conclusion, their results suggest that SLS was the most common diabetic complication among Jewish and Arab IDDM patients.^[21]

In a study, total of 142 patients (68%) had at least one cutaneous disorder, and 81 patients (38%) had skin lesions considered to be associated with diabetes. The most prevalent cutaneous manifestation was xerosis, found in 22% of type 1 diabetic patients. In control subjects, the ichthyosiform changes affected only 3% of the children and adolescents. The difference was highly significant ($P < 0.01$). Thyroid-stimulating hormone levels were normal in all patients with diabetic hand (scleroderma-like changes and/or limited joint mobility).^[22] The prevalence of scleroderma spectrum disorders (including systemic sclerosis [SSC] meeting the American Rheumatism Association criteria and the less typical disorders meeting only the study criteria) was determined in a random sample of 6,998 subjects from the general population of South Carolina. The results suggested that the prevalence of these disorders might range from 67 to 265 per 100,000, which was 4.9 to 19.2 times higher than previously reported for definite SSC. The ratio of nondefinite cases to definite cases of SSC (those meeting American Rheumatism Association criteria) was 2.5. Most of the nondefinite cases were unrecognized prior to the study, which suggests the need for improved early diagnosis of scleroderma spectrum disorders. Brief histories of the 7 patients

with scleroderma spectrum disorders were reported.^[23]

In another study, diabetic hand, a variety of sclerodermoid lesions in diabetic patients, was seen in only 2.3% of our patients but was strongly related to diabetes duration ($P < 0.001$). In young patients with type 1 diabetes with three-times-longer disease duration, the prevalence of scleroderma-like changes of the hand was 39%.^[24] In our study the incidence of waxy skin was 41 (32.8%) cases in diabetic group and 25 (20%) cases in non diabetic group. The difference was statistically significant. In the diabetic group out of 41 cases there were 17 cases with skin thick over dorsum of hands especially fingers, 13 cases with pebbling of skin over knuckles, 10 cases with waxy skin and 1 case with skin thick over both dorsum of hands and feet. Except for one case all the above cases had age more than 40 years with family history of diabetes positive in most of the cases and duration of diabetes ranged from first time detected diabetics to more than 10 years. In non diabetic group out of 25 cases, 15 cases had skin thick over dorsum of hands especially over fingers. 7 cases had pebbling of skin over knuckles and 3 cases had waxy skin. Majority of the above cases had family history of diabetes positive and age more than 40 years. We have recorded one case of scleroedema diabeticorum in diabetic group only, the incidence being 1 (0.8%). This finding was in variance with the study of Cole et al (1983) where the prevalence of scleroedema was 3% in patients with NIDDM.

CONCLUSION

Among the disorders of collagen most common was waxy skin observed in 32.8% of cases which was statistically significant when compared with non diabetic group. We even had one case each of necrobiosis lipoidica diabeticorum, granuloma annulare and scleroedema diabeticorum. From the foregoing account it became clear that the skin is involved in diabetics quite often. The manifestations are numerous and many a times they can serve as diagnostic markers for the underlying undetected diabetes. So whenever patients present with multiple manifestations their diabetic status should be checked and controlled, or if they are obese and have positive family history of diabetes mellitus, a high index of suspicion should be kept regarding their diabetic status. In this way diabetes can be detected quite early and early intervention can prevent morbidity from this deadly disease. Sports physicians and patients with diabetes should be aware of these manifestations, so that optimal physiotherapy programmes can be devised that do not exacerbate existing complaints and encourage continuing physical activity in this group.

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Medico-legal study on natural deaths

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Abstract

Background and Objectives: Pulmonary Tuberculosis is an important cause of natural death in relation to respiratory system that may occur rapidly or suddenly, and hence has a medico-legal importance.

To know the exact prevalence of different cases of pulmonary tuberculosis within the cases of natural death examined in the medico-legal institute of Baghdad.

Method: The study was conducted within 6 months period in the medico-legal institute of Baghdad on 241 cases of natural deaths referred from different investigation authorities. After collecting the required information and knowing the circumstances of death, classical and complete autopsy was done for each case followed by complementary lab investigation including tissue samples for histopathological examination using H&E stain.

In addition to that photography was done for some interesting cases.

Results: Natural death cases constituted 22% of all medico-legal cases referred for autopsy while violent causes of death constituted the rest (78%) during the study. Death due to cardiovascular diseases was 46% of all natural death cases followed by respiratory diseases which were 30%. Pneumonia was the commonest respiratory disease leading to death constituted 57% followed by pulmonary TB 28% and Tuberculous pneumonia 7%. Most deaths due to pulmonary TB occurred within the age groups 30-40 and 40-50 years.

Conclusions: 1. Respiratory diseases were the second highest numbers after cardiovascular diseases leading to natural death. 2. Pulmonary TB was the second commonest respiratory disease after pneumonia in causation of natural death. 3. The results above denote the importance for the attention to Pulmonary TB regarding its prevention and treatment in our country to decrease its mortality rate. 4. Natural sudden death cases constituted a lower percentage of all cases referred for autopsy. 5. The study reflects the importance of medico-legal anatomical studies for different medical branches.

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Keywords: Tuberculosis, Tuberculous pneumonia, Sudden death, Autopsy.

INTRODUCTION

Sudden death is defined as the death that occurs rapidly and unexpectedly in a previously apparently healthy individuals or due to a mysterious disease within 24 hours after the onset of symptoms and when clinical examination and lab. investigation failed to diagnose the cause of death [1, 2, 3, 4].

Usually classification of the causes of sudden natural death is done according to different body systems and cardiovascular system occupies the first

most common system leading to natural death especially coronary artery diseases [2].

Respiratory diseases come next. They constituted 23% of all natural death in a previous study in United States [3].

Pneumonia in its different types was the commonest type of respiratory diseases as it was found that 4-6 per 100 children are infected with pneumonia annually according to a study done in North Carolina [5].

One of the chronic respiratory diseases that leads to sudden natural death is Pulmonary TB which seldom causes death in developed countries. In Wales it constituted only 0.5% of all deaths due to respiratory diseases. While in developing countries it is still considered one of main causes of natural death. In Baghdad during the period between the years 1948 -1978 pulmonary tuberculosis reached 1.3- 5.35 % of all cases referred to autopsy and 5 - 16 % of all

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natural deaths and 20 - 60 % of all respiratory diseases with male to female ratio almost 4:1 . Most of the death occurred above the 7th decade of life and during winter season. Their autopsies revealed tuberculous cavitations in almost all cases examined [6, 7, 8].

In a forensic medical survey conducted during the period between the years 1989 - 1991 on death due to respiratory diseases, pulmonary tuberculosis occupied 14.8% [9].

Pathologically pulmonary tuberculosis starts as a primary focus in the upper lobes of the lungs between the alveoli. The tubercle consists of a central caseous necrosis surrounded by langerhans giant cells, macrophages and lymphocytes, plasma cell and fibroblasts and with time these tubercles will extend to the regional lymph nodes around the trachea on the same side to constitute Ghon Complex. This complex may be surrounded by fibrosis to remain dormant for long period giving the infected person some immunity against the disease or it may be reactivated causing another tuberculous infection [10, 11].

Acute infection is usually seen in persons with deficient immunity presented as tuberculous pneumonia or bronchopneumonia while chronic infection is more complicated as it may occur in the top and the base of the lungs at the same time and presented in acute and chronic infection and is seen in a tuberculous lymph node of scar or open tuberculous cavity. Sudden death occurs due to sever pulmonary bleeding resulted from vascular erosion in a tuberculous cavity or as a result of sudden and sever tuberculous pneumonia [2, 3].

The causative agents for tuberculosis are:

- 1- Mycobacterium Tuberculosis.
- 2- Atypical tuberculosis by M.Kansasii
- 3- M.Avium [10, 11].

METHODS

The study was conducted in the Medico-legal Institute of Baghdad during 6 months period starting from the first of October 2002 till the end of March 2003.

A total number of 241 cases of natural death were included in this descriptive study. Information and other related data with circumstances of death were collected from close relatives, eye witnesses and police reports.

Complete and classical autopsy was done for all cases including gross inspection with photography of some interesting finding followed by tissue sampling from various organs for histopathological examination using H & E stain to confirm the diagnosis.

Some statistical means were used to reveal the differences between the results to be shown in figures and tables.

RESULTS

The study revealed that natural death cases were 22% of the total number of all deaths referred to the medico-legal institute in Baghdad while violent death cases were 78% as it is shown in figure no. 1.

Death due to cardiovascular diseases were the commonest causes among natural death cases constituting 46% while they were 10.3% of the total death cases.

Death due to respiratory diseases were the second commonest causes of natural death constituting 30 % while they were 6.6% of the total number of cases as it is shown in table-1.

Pneumonia was the commonest cause of death among respiratory diseases reaching to 57% followed by pulmonary tuberculosis and tuberculous pneumonia in 28 % and 7% respectively as shown in table -2.

Figure-1: Shows number of deaths and their percentage.

Body system	Respiratory system	Cardiovascular system	Nervous system	Gastrointestinal system	Genitourinary system	total
number	72	111	46	7	5	241
Percentage n=241	30%	46%	19%	3%	2%	100%
Percentage from the total n=1076	6.6%	10.03%	4.2%	0.6%	0.4%	100%

Table-1: Numbers of natural death cases according to body systems

Type of disease	pneumonia	Tuberculosis	Tuberculous pneumonia	Air embolism	Bronchial asthma	Total
Number	41	20	5	5	1	72
percentage	57%	28%	7%	7%	1%	100%

Table-2: Types of respiratory diseases diagnosed by postmortem exam.

Type of disease	Past medical history	Total number	Percentage from the total number n=72
Tuberculosis	12	20	16.6%
Bronchial asthma	1	1	1.3%
Tuberculous pneumonia	5	5	6.9%

Table-3: Past medical history among respiratory causes of death.

Figure-2:Gross appearance of pulmonary tuberculosis showing caseation on both lung lobes surfaces and pleura.

Figure-3 : Microscopical section of pulmonary tuberculous granuloma showing langerhans giant cells [X10].

Figure-4: Microscopial section of pulmonary tuberculous granuloma showing langerhans giant cells and epithelioid cells [X100].

Figure-5: Gross appearance of tuberculous pneumonia , cavitations with upper lobes with consolidation of the lower lobes and around the trachea.

Nineteen male were infected with pulmonary tuberculosis while only one female contracted the disease. Four males died due to tuberculous pneumonia and only one female died due to the same disease. Only 18 cases were with past medical history for tuberculosis resembling 25% of all autopsy cases. Twelve of them were with past medical history for pulmonary tuberculosis and 5 cases were contracting tuberculous pneumonia while only one case with bronchial asthma (table-3). Most of the death cases due to pulmonary tuberculosis were within the age groups 30-40 and 40-50 years. Indoor death cases due to respiratory diseases were 44 out of 72 accounting 61.1%. Figures 2,3,4,5 show gross appearance of pulmonary tuberculosis, microscopic appearance of tuberculous granuloma magnified 100 times and 1000 times and gross appearance of tuberculous pneumonia respectively.

DISCUSSION

Sudden death cases are under the responsibility of forensic pathologists because of their vague circumstances of death and the short period they happened after the appearance of symptoms and as well as the probability of interference of other factors in causation of death [12]. Respiratory diseases are considered one of the main causes of sudden natural death that may reach up to 23% of all sudden death in developed countries. In this study it is accounting 30% (table-1).

The study revealed that the main cause of death related to the respiratory system was pneumonia reached up to 41 cases accounting 57% (table-2). This finding is in agreement with other local studies done by Al-Gurairy and Ghazi [9]. Pulmonary tuberculosis death is considered the second most common cause after pneumonia accounting 28% of all respiratory diseases (table-2). This is explained by the abnormal circumstances of the country during the study and the prevalence of malnutrition deficient vaccination and shortage of drugs in treating tuberculosis patients. In addition to that shortage in materials used in radiological and lab. diagnosis of the disease moreover poor commitment of the patients for their medical advice and drug intake with lack of follow up which all will subsequently lead fatal complications specially tuberculous pneumonia which is accounting 7% of all respiratory diseases in this study (table-2). This percentage is considered very high in comparison with the percentages in the developing countries in which pulmonary tuberculosis does not exceed 0.5% of all deaths due to respiratory diseases [6]. But the results of this study are in agreement with a previous study done in Baghdad during 1984 by Hassan and Hanna [8].

This study and the similar studies disclosed that natural death cases referred for autopsy were small in numbers. This is due to the medico-legal system implemented in our country which is similar to the European Continental System in helping the police to detect the crimes.

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Sero-prevalence of human immunodeficiency virus, hepatitis B and C viruses among intending blood donors attending university of Abuja teaching hospital, Gwagwalada, Fct Abuja. Nigeria

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Abstract

Background: Transfusion transmissible infectious agents such as the human immunodeficiency virus, Hepatitis B and C viruses continues to be a major public health problem worldwide, hence screening of blood and blood products for these pathogens is required.

Aim: To determine the sero-prevalence of human immunodeficiency virus, Hepatitis B and C among blood donors attending the university of Abuja teaching hospital, Gwagwalada, federal capital city, Abuja.

Methods: A retrospective analysis of consecutive blood donors' records covering the period between August 2010 and March 2011 was conducted to determine screening outcome for HIV, HBV and anti-HCV and the association between their age groups and sex were analyzed. Sterile venous blood was collected from each of the donors and analyzed for HIV, HBV and anti-HCV using highly sensitive and specific kits.

Result: Of the 1039 samples analyzed, 61 were positive for HIV, 107 for HBV and 46 for HCV, representing a prevalence of 5.9%, 10.3% and 4.4% respectively among intending blood donors. 13 (1.3%) had multiple infections, the most common combinations were HIV - HBV 9 (69.2%) and least was HBV - HCV 1 (7.8%). The seropositivity of HIV was significantly increased among female blood donors while HCV was highest among male blood donors. Seropositivity to the infections was highest in the age group 30-39 years.

Conclusions: Transfusion transmissible infections is present in a substantial percentage of blood donors in this study area. Strict selection of blood donors and comprehensive screening of donors' blood using standard methods are highly recommended to ensure the safety of blood for recipient.

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Keywords: Seroprevalence, TTTS, HIV, HBV, HCV, blood donors, Gwagwalada

INTRODUCTION

Transfusion transmissible infections continues to be a major blood transfusion problem worldwide, most especially in Africa and in the tropics where national blood transfusion services

and policies, appropriate infrastructures, trained personnel and financial resources are inadequate [1]. Human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), hepatitis B virus (HBV) and hepatitis C virus (HCV) are of great

concern because of their prolonged viraemia and carrier or latent state. They also cause fatal, chronic and life-threatening disorders. Blood transfusion accounts for 5-10% of HIV infections in sub-Saharan Africa [2]. Similarly, 12.5% of patients who received blood transfusion are at risk of post transfusion hepatitis [3]. Because of the current blood banking system which encourages non-remunerated or voluntary donation especially to relatives who are hospitalized, we have had occasions to screen all intending donors. Since screening includes blood grouping, serological screening for human immunodeficiency virus (HIV), hepatitis B (HBV), hepatitis C (HCV) and syphilis, it has made it mandatory for donors to be screened for these diseases of global importance. Since last decade both HIV and HBV infections have drawn global attention owing to their grievous public health impact.

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HIV infection is caused by a retrovirus known as human immunodeficiency virus (type 1 and 2) which breaks down the body's immune system and leads to acquired immune deficiency syndrome (AIDS) leaving the person susceptible to opportunistic infections and some malignancies [4]. AIDS in humans was first reported in 1981 in USA and HIV was first isolated in 1983 [5]. Since then, it has killed more than 25 million people in the world. The first two cases of HIV and AIDS in Nigeria were identified in 1985, and were reported at an international AIDS conference in 1986 [6]. At first the Nigerian government was slow to respond to the increasing rates of HIV transmission and it was only in 1991 that the Federal Ministry of Health made their first attempt to assess Nigeria's AIDS situation [7]. By the end of 2009 it was estimated that there will be only one HIV testing and counseling facility for approximately every 53,000 Nigerian adults, which shows how desperately the government needs to scale up HIV testing services [8].

Statistics show that by the end of 2009, about 3 million people were living with HIV in Nigeria [6]. However, the National Agency for the Control of AIDS (NACA) has just launched its National Strategic Framework to cover 2010 to 2015 [6]. This Framework is to reach 80 percent of sexually active adults and 80 percent of most at-risk populations with HIV counseling and testing by 2015; ensure 80 percent of eligible adults and 100 percent of eligible children are receiving ART by 2015; and to improve access to quality care and support services to at least 50 percent of people living with HIV by 2015 [7]. Nigeria, therefore, still has a long way to go in combating its devastating AIDS epidemic.

HBV is highly contagious and relatively easy to be transmitted from one infected individual to another by blood transfusion, during birth, by unprotected sex, and by sharing needles and has a relatively higher prevalence in the tropics [8, 9]. It is estimated that nearly 2 billion people around the world have serologic evidence of past or present HBV infection, while 350 million people are chronically infected [10]. The prevalence of HBV is highest among the developing countries of Asia, Africa and the Pacific Islands and lowest among the developed countries of America, Europe and Australia [11].

HCV, on the other hand, is the principal cause of parenterally transmitted non-A, non-B hepatitis [12]. This blood-borne virus affects 200 million people worldwide, and an estimated 3.0% (170 million) of the world's population is chronically infected with HCV [13]. HIV, HBV, and HCV all have similar modes of transmission; however, HCV has low sexual transmission [13]. The most efficient mode of transmission of HCV is direct percutaneous exposure to infectious blood [10]. Of persons newly infected with HCV, only 20.0% to 30.0 % have symptoms of acute hepatitis, and the highest prevalence of HCV

infection (70.0% to 90.0%) is reported among those persons with substantial or repeated direct percutaneous exposures to blood, such as intravenous drug users, persons with hemophilia treated with clotting factor concentrates that did not undergo viral inactivation, and recipients of transfusion from HCV- positive donors [14]. Data is very scarce on the seroprevalence of HIV, HBV and HCV among intending blood donors of Gwagwalada, Federal capital city, Abuja and its environs. The high prevalence of blood borne infectious diseases has increased the problem of blood transfusion. A prerequisite for blood safety is a continuous monitoring of trends and magnitude of transfusion transmissible infections in blood donors. This study aim therefore to determine the seroprevalence of HIV, HBV and HCV among intending blood donors at the University of Abuja teaching hospital, Gwagwalada, Federal capital territory (FCT), Abuja.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was carried out in the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital (UATH), Gwagwalada, Federal capital territory, Nigeria from August 2010-March 2011. The hospital is a tertiary health care facility with a referral status to the many district general hospitals owned by the FCT administration, military hospitals and private hospitals in the federal capital city. It has an effective blood banking system catering for all the blood needs of patients admitted in the hospital. Health data for intending 1039 non-remunerated and replacement blood donors who attended the blood donor's bank of the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Gwagwalada, Abuja between the August 2010 and March 2011 were collected. Verbal informed consent was obtained from the authorities of the blood bank and the protocol for this study was approved by the Ethical Committee of the University of Abuja Teaching Hospital.

Specimen collection and analysis

Blood samples were collected aseptically by veni-puncture from the donors and were analyzed for blood group, HIV 1 & 2, HBV and HCV. Determine® HIV-1/2 Test cards (manufactured by Inverness Medical, Japan), Unigold™ Kit (manufactured by Trinity Biotech, Ireland) and HIV -1/2 Stat- Pak® Assay (manufactured by Chembio Diagnostic Systems, USA) were used in a stepwise order for the detection of HIV-1 and HIV-2 in the blood. These methods which are immunochromatographic and qualitative in nature, detect the presence of antibodies to HIV-1 and HIV-2 in human blood and can be read in-vitro having more than 99.9%

sensitivity and 99.75% specificity. Rapid lateral chromatographic Immunoassay kit (WHOBC- Acon Biotech, Hangzhou, China) and a rapid visual immunoassay Kit (WHOBC - Labman, Hamburg, Germany) were used to detect the HBsAg and anti-HCV in the blood of study population, which is also a fairly reliable test having more than 99.9% sensitivity and specificity. It is also an in-vitro diagnostic test done by enzyme linked immunochromatographic method and gives qualitative visual read results.

Data analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS version 16.0 and an independent T-test method. Significance was determined at $P < 0.05$.

RESULT

Out of the 1039 subjects (749 males and 290 females) tested serologically for HIV, HBV and HCV, 61 (5.9%) were HIV positive, 107(10.3%) were HBsAg positive and 46 (4.4%) were anti-HCV positive (Fig 1). Males had higher seroprevalence of HBV and Anti-HCV with HIV Having a higher prevalence in intending female blood donors (Table 1). Age group wise distribution of HIV, HBV and Anti-HCV is shown in Table 2. 13 (1.3%) intending blood donors had mixed infections, the most common combinations were HIV- HBV 9 (69.2%) and least was HIV - HCV 1 (7.8%) (Table 3).

Figure- 1: Percentage occurrence of HIV, HBV and HCV among the blood donors.

Table 1: Gender related prevalence of HIV, HBV and HCV among blood donors

Sex	Total subjects	HIV No. Infected. %	HBV No. Infected. %	HCV. No Infected %
Male	749(72.1)	40(5.3)	73(9.7)	35(4.7)
Female	290(27.9)	21(7.2)	34(11.7)	11(3.8)

Table 2: Age wise distribution of HIV, HBV and Anti-HCV

Age	Total subjects	HIV No. Infected. (%)	HBV No. infected (%)	HCV No. Infected (%)
Below 20	113(10.9)	5(4.4)	7(6.2)	3(2.7)
20-29	426(41.0)	19(4.5)	31(7.3)	20(4.7)
30-39	420(40.4)	34(8.0)	51(12.1)	23(5.5)
Above 40	170(16.4)	3(1.76)	18(10.6)	2(1.2)
Total	1039	61(5.9)	107(10.3)	46(4.4)

Table 3: Prevalence of co-infections of HIV, HBV, HCV and syphilis among blood donors at University of Abuja Teaching Hospital, Gwagwalada, Abuja.

Co-infections	Number Infected (%)
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HIV and HBV	9 (69.2)
HIV and HCV	4(30.8)
HBV and HCV	1(7.8)
Total	13(1.3)

DISCUSSION

Infections acquired during blood transfusion continue to be a major global health problem in transfusion medicine; therefore no effort should be spared at reducing this complication to the barest minimum. It is important due to the known long term mortality and morbidity associated with infections caused by HIV, Hepatitis B and C, to monitor the trend in the prevalence of these infections so as to ascertain the risk of the infections in our donor pool. A total of 61 (5.9%) out of the 1039 subjects screened were seropositive for HIV, while 107 (10.3%) and 46 (4.4%) were positive respectively for HBV and HCV. The prevalence recorded in this study area are similar with 5.5%, 10.3% and 5.71% seroprevalence for HIV, HBV and HCV among intending blood donors in Maiduguri, Jos and Benin City [15, 16, 17]. Higher prevalence has been recorded for HIV in Nigeria and Hepatitis B in Ethiopia [19]. The high prevalence of HBV and HCV could well be attributed to the low level awareness about the diseases; as such there is urgent need for public health intervention programmes aimed at educating the general populace on the severity of these diseases.

HIV sero prevalence was higher in female blood donors than in the males. The significantly increased HIV seropositivity among female donors compared to male donors is in accordance with previous report [20]. This significantly increased HIV seropositivity among female donors might be due to their increased vulnerability to HIV infection as a result of biological, social and economic disadvantages related to their Gender [21]. The diseases studied are fairly age specific and behavior dependent, people of age 20-40 years have been found to be more sexually and economically the most active group and these diseases are at high prevalence in those groups [17, 22]. In the present study HIV seroprevalence was highest in the age group 30-39 followed by age group 20-29, this report is similar to earlier reports [17, 22, 23].

Our study reveals that the prevalence of HBV infection among the blood donors of UATH, Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja as well as in the case of the entire country Nigeria has increased over the years; this is evidenced by reports from different parts of

the country; 46.83% from Benin city [17], 13.22% from Ibadan [24], 10.6(%) from Jos [16]. A recent study in this hospital (UATH) using pregnant women as subjects also recorded a high sero prevalence of HBV, 19 (9.5%) out of 200 studied. This result and ours confirms the high burden of HBV in this study area. As earlier pointed out, lack of knowledge of disease transmission modes, severity of infection and its mortality rate has contributed to the high prevalence. Data also agree that there exists a high endemicity for HBV in other parts of Africa [17] and potentiates the fact that hepatitis B is on the increase. With the exception of Tunisia and Morocco which have intermediate endemicity and Zambia which has intermediate/high endemicity, most countries in Africa including Nigeria have high endemicity for hepatitis B. This clearly explains the reason behind the high seroprevalence obtained in our study. The result of this study is quite different from those obtained from other parts of the world such as Australia with 0.01% [25], Iran with 0.56% [26] and India with 0.66% [27]. Presence of occult hepatitis B virus in blood donors is considered a potential risk for transfusion of hepatitis B virus and that is why screening for occult hepatitis B infection through the use of nucleic acid testing (NAT) of blood donors has been adopted in advanced countries. Low levels of HBV-DNA remain detectable, through NAT, in serum and liver tissue in some patients who cleared HBsAg from acute self-limited infection [28] and can result in overt hepatitis B infection, particularly when such blood is transfused to immunocompromised patients [29]. The use of NAT could have probably been responsible for the reduction of the prevalence of hepatitis B infection in the developed world as shown by the significantly low values reported. Further studies are being carried out in our study area using molecular methods (NAT) to determine the prevalence of HBV -DNA in HBV sero positive samples, this will be reported later.

The prevalence of anti-HCV in intending blood donors in this commune is higher than earlier reports from other parts of the country [24, 30, 31] but concurs with a recent study by Dirisu *et al* and Jesse *et al* [17, 32]. Higher prevalence has been reported in studies done in sub-Saharan Africa countries; Matee *et al*. [33] reported 8.0% in their study in Tanzania, 8.4% was reported by Ampofo *et al*. from Ghana [34] and 7.6% from Egypt [35]. Where there are no materials to carryout screening for HCV using molecular methods, efforts should be maintained at keeping false

negative anti-HCV in our donated units low through stringent donor criteria and excluding subjects with high risk behaviors as studies have shown that the most efficient mode of transmission of HCV is blood to blood contact [36], less efficiently through sexual route unlike HBV and HIV infection [37].

In the study, co-infections were recorded among intending blood donors with HIV- HBV co-infection being highly prevalent, this is in agreement with reports from recent studies [38,39]. Multiple infections with Human immunodeficiency virus, Hepatitis B and C viruses are probably in line with common route of transmission of most of these agents, which are direct contact with blood, intravenous drug injections, transfusion of blood and blood products, and sexual activity. Intravenous drug usage cannot be said to be a problem in our environment presently, however, sexual activity and blood and blood products transfusion are major sources of transmission. Studies have shown that multiple co-infections, particularly hepatitis B and hepatitis C virus dual infection are associated with substantial risk of fulminant hepatitis, and a more severe histological lesion [40], and poor response to therapy [40]. HCV infection has also been shown to suppress HBV replication and with low HBV-DNA levels, decreased HBV-DNA polymerase activity, and decreased expression of HBsAg expression in blood [40] which may lead to false HBsAg negativity thereby presenting as occult hepatitis. In view of this, HBV co-infection with HCV should not be excluded by mere negative HBsAg status alone [41].

A major limitation of this study being a retrospective one was the inability to gather information about the socio-economic status and behavioral patterns as these are major indices in measuring the prevalence of infections. The seroprevalence data, behavioral patterns and socio-economic status of our community indicates that there is a high potential for the spread of HIV, HBV and HCV in Gwagwalada, FCT Abuja, Nigeria. We conclude that in UATH, Gwagwalada, transfusion transmissible infections is highly prevalent with some intending donors having mixed infections. Transmission of transfusion-transmissible infections during the serologically negative window period still pose a threat to blood safety in environments where there is a high rate of transfusion-transmissible infection. It is therefore thought germane that strict procedure be employed in the selection of blood donors with the emphasis on getting voluntary donors and comprehensive screening of donors' blood for HIV, HBV and HCV using standard methods are highly recommended to ensure the safety of blood for recipient.

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The hemodialysis effectiveness on lipid per oxidation and carnation levels in hemodialaysis patients

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Abstract

Background: Carnation is a small molecule widely present in all cells from prokaryotic to eukaryotic. It is an important element in β -oxidation of fatty acids. Carnation is a scavenger of oxygen free radicals in mammalian tissue. Lack of carnitine in hemodialysis patient can lead to carnitine deficiency. Oxidation of fatty acid and lipid metabolism are severly affected in carnitine deficiency. Oxidative stress defines as imbalance between formation of free radicals and antioxidative defense mechanisms. It has been proposed to play a role in many disease states. In hemodialysis patient multiple factor can lead to a high susceptibility to oxidative stress. The aim of this study was to determination of hemodialysis effectiveness on change rate of serum L-carnitine and lipid peroxidation.

Methods: This research is an analytic study. 27 chronic renal failure patients (24-80 yr) who undergo hemodialysis (6-12 month) were selected (M= 17, F= 10). Malondialdehyde (MDA), as indicator of lipid peroxidation was measured colorimetrically with standard Thiobarbituric acid (TBA) method. Also L-carnitine was measured with enzymatic UV method (Rouche kit) (Spectronic Genesis 2, 340 nm).

Results: The weight mean of L-carnitine before and after hemodialysis was respectively (7.67 ± 3.6 mg/l, 2.07 ± 1.6 mg/l) ($P < 0.001$). The weight mean of pre-hemodialysis MDA was (4.17 ± 1.24 μ mol/l), following hemodialysis (4.98 ± 1.2 μ mol/l) ($P < 0.001$). Results showed 55.6% of patient suffered from carnitine deficiency. Serum carnitine can decrease markedly after hemodialysis ($P < 0.001$).

Conclusion: Our findings indicated that oxidative stress in these patients, which is further exacerbated by hemodialysis, as evidenced by increased lipid peroxidation. Pearson correlation coefficient, indicated the relation between differ average of serum L-carnitine and serum MDA before and after hemodialysis ($r = 0.82$, $r = 0.75$).

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Keywords: Carnation, Hemodialysis, Kidney failure chronic, Lipid Per oxidation, Oxidative stress

INTRODUCTION

L-carnitine is an essential factor for the membrane transport of acyl-CoA compounds, particularly for the intramitochondrial transport of long-chain fatty acids. L-carnitine also helps to remove by-products of fatty acid metabolism and other toxic compounds from the cells [1].

The liver and kidney represent the main sources of endogenous carnitine synthesis. Also among the homeostatic processes controlling the endogenous L-carnitine pool in humans, the kidney has a vital role through extensive and adaptive tubular reabsorption [2]. Kidney disease can lead to disturbances in L-carnitine homeostasis, and carnitine deficiency may occur in hemodialysis patients. Bellinghieri et al reported that hemodialysis may promote excessive losses of L-carnitine [3].

Oxidation of fatty acid and lipid metabolism are severly affected in carnitine deficiency [4]. Aberrant fatty acid metabolism has been associated with the pro-motion of free-radical production insulin resistance and cellular apoptosis [5]. Oxidant stress by definition is a biochemical condition in which oxidant species over whelms antioxidant defenses ultimately leading to a given biological damage [6, 7]. Galli F, et al indicated the evidence for the presence of oxidant stress in hemodialysis

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patients [8]. In these patients multiple factor can lead to a high susceptibility to oxidative stress [9, 10].

One of the most investigated biological effects of the oxidative stress in hemodialysis patients is lipid peroxidation [11].

In the view of the above, the aim of this study was to determination of hemodialysis effectiveness on change rate of serum L-carnitine and lipid peroxidation.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemical: Thiobarbituric acid (TBA), Buthylated Hydroxy Tuloene (BHT) and other reagents are purchased from Sigma (Deisenhofen, Germany) or Merck (Parmstadt, Germany). Also L-carnitine kit (Rouche) is used.

Subjects: This research was an analysis study. 27 patients with chronic renal failure on hemodialysis were used in the analysis. All patients were dialyzed 3 times/wk for 4 hr each session. The duration of dialysis was (6-12 month). The age of patients was (24-48 yr). The patients were not taking any antioxidants. Diabetic patients were excluded from the study. The demographic information written in a check-list form. All hemodialysis objects were digitally and type of filter was (R_s).

Venous blood samples were taken in an EDTA-anticoagulated tube (1 g/l) after an overnight fast immediately before and after the dialysis session. Plasma was separated by centrifugation at 3000 g for 5 min at 4° C.

MDA Assay: Malondialdehyde (MDA), as indicator of lipid peroxidation was measured colorimetrically with standard TBA method at 532 nm [12, 13].

L-carnitine Assay: L-carnitine concentration was measured with enzymatic UV-method and spectronic Genesis, 340 nm.

Statistical analysis: All results are presented as mean±standard deviation. Leven test, paired t-test, independent t-test was used for rejection or acceptance of the assumption. Pearson correlation coefficient was used for correlation.

RESULTS

The weight mean of serum L-carnitine, before and after hemodialysis was respectively 7.67±3.6 mg/l. In this study 55.6% of patients suffered from carnitine deficiency (P<0.001). Pearson correlation coefficient indicated the relation between the value of serum L-carnitine in before and after hemodialysis (r=0.4 , P=0.045).The statistical results showed the significant difference between the value of serum L-carnitine before and after hemodialysis (P<0.001) (Table 1).Also weight mean of pre-hemodialysis and Post-hemodialysis serum MDA was respectively 4.17±1.24 µmol/l and 4.98±1.2. Pearson correlation coefficient indicated that there is strong relative between serum MDA before and after hemodialysis (r=0.96 , P<0.01).Also statistical results showed that there is significant differences between the value of serum MDA before and after hemodialysis (P<0.01) , that increases after hemodialysis (Table 2).Pearson correlation coefficient indicated the relation between differ average of serum L-carnitine and serum MDA before and after hemodialysis (r=0.82 , r=0.75).

The graph of confident interval of percentage of change average of L-carnitine and MDA is drawn(graph 1).

Parameter	Sex	Number	Mean±SD	Weight mean	P-value
L-carnitine	Male	17	8.96±3.66	7.67±3.6	0.053
(before hemodialysis)	Female	10	5.93±2.88		
L-carnitine	Male	17	2.66±1.67	2.07±1.6	0.01*
(before hemodialysis)	Female	10	1.06±0.85		
L-carnitine differ	Male	17	6.03±3.69	--	0.045
	Female	10	4.86±2.6		

Table-1 : Mean and standard deviation of L-carnitine in female and male also their differ and differ percent . * indicated that there is difference between male and female. Statistical tests: independent t-test and Leven test.

Parameter	Sex	Number	Mean±SD	Weight mean	P-value
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MDA	Male	17	3.75±0.91	4.17±1.24	0.048*
(before hemodialysis)	Female	10	4.87±1.45		
MDA(before hemodialysis)	Male	17	4.63±1.11	4.98±1.2	0.05*
	Female	10	5.57±1.16		
MDA differ	Male	17	0.88±0.28	--	0.05
	Female	10	0.7±0.4		

Table-2 : Mean and standard deviation of MDA in female and male also their differ and differ percent
 * indicated that there is difference between male and female. Statistical tests: independent t-test and Leven test.

Graph -1 : The confident interval of percentage of change average of serum L-carnitine and serum MDA in female and male

DISCUSSION

Existing evidence showed that despite advances in dialysis therapy, a high percentage of patients on maintenance dialysis therapy, suffered from complication of hemodialysis [14]. The study of Evans et al showed, the average of predialysis serum L-carnitine concentration was 19.5 µmol/l, where as the post dialysis level was 5.6 µmol/l [4]. Also Alhomida's research indicated that the average of serum L-carnitine before and after hemodialysis was 42±6.3 µmol/l and 17.1±6.3 µmol/l [15]. This study is

consistent with other study and showed decrease after hemodialysis.

L-carnitine is a small water-soluble molecules, therefore it is freely dialyzed, because of a molecular weight gradient, the acyl carnitine moieties are less likely to be filtered by the membrane than free carnitine [2,16]. Accumulation of acyl carnitine is belived to contribute directly to arrythmo genesis [17]. Also this accumulation, altered mitochondrial membrane permeability and has been suggested to promote apoptosis. Altered membrane permeability has been implicated in modifying the activity of

various hormone receptors. Including insulin receptors [18].

The susceptibility for oxidative stress is mainly correlated with MDA concentration [19,20]. It has been reported that the hemodialysis procedure altered lipid peroxidation, Ozden et al found that MDA was elevated in post-hemodialysis in comparison to prehemodialysis (post hemodialysis 1.39 ± 0.38 nmol/ml, pre hemodialysis 0.83 ± 0.22 nmol/l) [21], but Nand and Surri showed that MDA was decreased after hemodialysis (pre hemodialysis 2.96 ± 0.89 μ mol/l and post hemodialysis 2.32 ± 0.84 μ mol/l) [22].

In this study we observed an increase of MDA, which possibly was the result of free radical reactions during the hemodialysis procedure. The absence of a complete correction of the uremic toxicity together with the untoward effect of the dialysis, malnutrition, and the progressive worsening of the clinical condition can lead to a high susceptibility to oxidative stress [23,24].

Increased lipid peroxidation in hemodialysis patient is largely a result of anemia of kidney failure, therefore anemia management can improve this condition [25,26] chronic heart failure in hemodialysis patients, has high prevalence, the researches indicated that lipid peroxidation and carnitine deficiency, are mainly factors in some of patients [27].

Multiple pathogenic factors are responsible for inter-dialytic muscle cramping. Carnitine deficiency is a potential cause of intradialytic muscle cramping [28,29]. Also oxidative damage may play a role in the pathogenesis of skeletal myopathy in hemodialysis patients [30]. Oxidative stress has been

proposed to play a role in many disease states, including cardiovascular and infectious disease [31,32], cancer [33], diabetes [34] and neurodegenerative pathologies [35]. Therefore oxidative stress management and supplementation with L-carnitine, parallel other therapeutic agent, may improve condition of hemodialysis patients.

In this study 55.6% of patients suffered from carnitine deficiency (before hemodialysis). Also serum L-carnitine can decrease markedly after hemodialysis ($P < 0.001$). In these patients, oxidative stress is further exacerbated by hemodialysis, as evidenced by increased lipid peroxidation ($P < 0.001$). Statistical results indicated that, there is correlation between the average of serum L-carnitine and serum MDA before and after hemodialysis ($r = 0.82$, $r = 0.75$).

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Thoracobiliary Fistula in Al-Jamhoori Teaching Hospital in Mosul

Mohammed Y. Al-Sheikh *

Abstract

Objective: Thoracobiliary fistulae are rare complications of echinococcosis due to rupture of intact Hydatid cyst and invasion of complicated Hydatid located at the upper surface of the liver to the thoracic cavity (pleura and lung); and extremely rare complication of thoracoabdominal trauma. We present our experience in treating the uncommon and dangerous entity with special interest on their attribute and outcomes.

Patients and Methods: during the last 8 years, 8 patients; 3 men, 4 women and one child ranging in age from 11 to 60 years with thoracobiliary fistulas were treated in our department. They presented with dyspnea, cough, fever, anemia, biloptesis. Diagnostic imaging (CXR, Ultrasonography of the abdomen, computed tomography of the abdomen and the chest with contrast) have been very helpful in identifying the communication and delineating its location. The disease was limited to pleural cavity in four cases, to pulmonary parenchyma in two cases, and in two was limited to bronchial tree.

Results: those patients having thoracobiliary fistula post traumatic have better prognosis than those patients having the fistula post Echinococcal liver infestation because those patients have had several operations, and they are usually severely ill with sepsis, malnutrition & respiratory problems in contrast to posttraumatic TBF patients have early diagnosis and better prognosis.

Conclusion: the echinococcosis is still endemic in our country so as the thoracoabdominal trauma. Thoracobiliary fistulae which complicate Echinococcal liver disease or Thoracoabdominal trauma still remains a serious complication with high morbidity and mortality. Early diagnosis and management of septic associated Complications are essential.

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Keywords: Thoracobiliary Fistula, Echinococcosis, Trauma, Al-Jamhoori Hospital, Mosul

INTRODUCTION

Thoracobiliary fistulae (TBF), a communication between the thoracic and biliary system which permits bile in the sputum or pleural cavity, are rare. TBF may communicate with either the pleural space (pleurobiliary fistula PBF) or the pulmonary parenchyma or bronchus (bronchobiliary fistula BBF).

Thoracobiliary fistulas are extremely rare, TBF have since been reported to be congenital[1], post-traumatic[2] to complicate inflammatory conditions (pyogenic liver abscesses[3], amoebic liver

abscesses[4], echinococcal[5] subphrenic abscess[6] or tuberculosis[7], malignant[8,9], and increasingly to follow interventional procedures, a complication of intrahepatic biliary stent migration^[10], and a complication of percutaneous transhepatic cholangiography[11]. Reports on the condition have largely been in the form of case reports. It is therefore not surprisingly that clear guidelines for the optimal treatment of TBF are lacking.

The aim of the study

In addressing this issue we report our experience in treating 8 patients with TBF.

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Patients and Method

Between the years 2000-2009; 8 cases of TBF were referred to thoracic unit at Al-Jumhoori hospital. We have received these patients with respect to etiology, clinical features, diagnosis, treatment and results. There were 3 men, 4 women and one child with the mean age of 45.3 (range from 4-60 years). Table (1) shows the details of 8 patients.

Table (1) patients details Summary of patient's details

Patient No.	AGE/ SEX	PRESENTION	AETIOLOGY	Outcome
1-	50/ female	Biliary Effusion	Ruptured Hydatid	Successful Surgery
2-	50/ female	Biliary Effusion	Ruptured Hydatid	Successful Surgery
3-	55/ female	Biloptysis	Ruptured Hydatid	Died
4-	11/ Child	Biliary Effusion	Thoracoabdominal Trauma (Blunt Trauma)	Successful Surgery
5-	54/ male	Rt lower Lobe Haziness	Hydatid cyst	Successful Surgery
6-	40/ male	Pneumonia Rt lower Lobe+fever	Subphrenic Abscess	Unsuccessful Surgery
7-	35/ male	Biliary Effusion	Thoracoabdominal Trauma (Penetrating Trauma)	Successful Surgery
8-	40/ female	Biloptysis	Ruptured Hydatid	Successful Surgery

In 6 patients the main etiological factor was chronic complicated hepatic echinococcosis but all these patients had previously undergone surgical interventions in the form of Laparotomy for removal of liver hydatid usually at the dome of diaphragm. In the rest 2 patients the main etiological factor was blunt thoracoabdominal trauma in one patients and penetrating thoracoabdominal by bullet in the other patients with liver laceration, these 2 patients had previously underwent surgical intervention in the form of Laparotomy (repair of liver laceration and subdiaphragmatic drain) .

All 8 patients had respiratory symptoms of cough,

sputum, SOB. Two patients had biloptysis. Four patients had external fistula through chest tube with bronchopleural fistula, one patient has anemia, fever, and chronic illness of 2 months following the Laparotomy. CXR demonstrate a right lower pneumonia in one patient, and haziness of right lower zone in the rest of the patients

CXR Shows RLL haziness& pleural effusion
pleural effusion.

Ultrasonography of the abdomen usually reveals subphrenic collection and liver diseases in the form of complicated Hydatid cyst. Computed tomography of the abdomen and chest reveals subphrenic collection, chronic liver disease in the form of complicated Hydatid cyst and the tract of fistula, and

CT of the chest and upper abdomen visualized the diaphragmatic tear and subdiaphragmatic collection, right side effusion.

Laboratory: usually shows leukocytosis and severe anemia in our cases.

All the patients underwent Right posterolateral thoracotomy as surgical intervention.

post operative CXR shows two chest tubes with clear lung field

Results

A total of 8 patients having TBF were included in this study, 6 of them were due to post echinococcal liver disease and 2 of them were due to post traumatic all underwent right posterolateral thoracotomy incision for excision of the fistula. All of them have successful surgery except one died during

operation due to cardiac arrest and one develop recurrent hydatid which necessitate re-thoracotomy and one patient develop bronchopleural fistula which necessitate muscle transposition and thorachoplasty .the two patients with post-trumatic TBF have successful surgery .

Discussion

The first description of TBF was that of Peacocks in 1850 in a patient with a hydatid cyst of the liver⁵. The second description of TBF 2nd to trauma was by Graham [12] in 1897. Ochsner described a 4% incidence of TBF in 453 pyogenic liver abscesses [3] and a 10.5% incidence of TBF in 3668 subphrenic abscess [6]. According to Morton and Philips [8], the second leading cause of thoracobiliary fistula other than hydatid, ecchinococcal or amoebic abscess of liver is obstruction of the CBD [13].

One of the main complications of the hydatid cyst of the superior surface of liver is its rupture into bronchial tree[14,15], this occurs due to continues pressure erosion from expanding hydatid cyst to diaphragm and the destructive effect of the superimposed infection, if enough adhesions encountered at pulmonary site, the cyst or the abscess will rupture into the pulmonary parenchyma causing pneumonitis and BBF[14,16], if no adhesions encountered at pulmonary site the cyst will rupture into pleural cavity causing biliary pleural effusion and pleurobiliary fistula[17] or even rupture into pericardium, great vessels , Figure 1 suggest way of TBF.

Thoracobiliary fistulas (BBF and PBF) are extremely rare complications following the thoracoabdominal trauma (penetrating and blunt). The exact incidence of TBF following the thoracoabdominal trauma is unknown, up to 1994 there was 34 cases of PBF reported in the English literatures and only 9 cases of BBF was recorded up to 1999. Anderson [18] discovered only 3 BBF following 1676

Thoracoabdominal injuries from the Second World War and the Korean conflict. Marr et al [18] on reviewing 153 gunshot wounds of the liver; had 13 bile leaks two of which were Thoracobiliary fistulas.

Figure 1 suggested way of TBF

Biliary fistulas occur in 2-4% of all cases of hepatic trauma, irrespective of the mechanism of injury [18]. The majority manifested as external cutaneous fistula through drain placed at surgery (intra-abdominal drain) or later on (thoracostomy tube) or as a localized intra-abdominal collection or free intraperitoneal leaks.

Thoracoabdominal trauma (blunt and penetrating) with hepatic injury is an ideal clinical setting with all the basic components required for the formation of TBF. The liver with disrupted biliary radicals and a lacerated diaphragm is necessary for establishment of PBF and in addition to this lung injury with an open bronchus sets the scene for the formation of BBF, so the incidence of BBF is high with penetrating thoracoabdominal injury. Where in PBF is more common with blunt trauma. Patients with PBF uniformly present with a persistent or delayed onset pleural effusion which contains bile, while patients with BBF present with chemical pneumonitis and coughing bile [18].

Abdominal U/S and CT scan were undertaken to identify predisposing hepatic pathology.

Sinogram shows external fistula

If an external fistula exists, a fistulogram is the best way to visualize the fistula in its absence, transhepatic cholangiography⁷ or endoscopic retrograde cholangiography may be used¹⁹. Cholescintigraphy using ¹³¹I rose Bengal has permitted preoperative diagnosis of TBF²⁰. But HIDA or PIPIDA Cholescintigraphy with delayed views are probably more reliable in detecting small BBF²¹. Presentation of these fistulas by early diagnosis and treatment of the underlying cause is extremely important since treatment of established TBF is usually very difficult. Those patients frequently have had several operations, and they are usually severely ill with sepsis, malnourished and having respiratory problems.

Once a TBF develops, cure is possible only with correction if possible biliary obstruction if present, adequate drainage of any concomitant abscess and of course treatment of underlying liver disease^{22, 23}. A two-stage approach can be used.

Stage one: external biliary drainage by percutaneous or surgical drainage of subphrenic abscess and, or direct percutaneous drainage of intrahepatic abscess, and thoracostomy tube for drainage of (biliary effusion).

Stage two: Those patients with TBF without biliary obstruction due to echinococcosis and trauma surgery still remain the treatment of choice. The approach of choice in our series was a right standard posterolateral thoracotomy because of the facility that offers in exposing both the lung and the liver, diaphragmatic disruption. The operation entails lysis of pulmonary adhesions (Decortication), minor & major pulmonary resection dealing with subdiaphragmatic liver disease, repair of diaphragmatic disruption, insertion of subdiaphragmatic drain, extended pulmonary resections are not justified taking into consideration on that echinococcosis has always the risk of recurrence and there is a vital need for sparing as much viable tissue as possible²³.

Conclusion

From this study with limited cases of TBF which complicate the echinococcal liver disease or thoracoabdominal trauma (blunt, penetrating) still remains a serious complication with high morbidity and mortality. Early diagnosis and management of septic associated complication are essential.

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Role of some medicinal plants in management of chronic bronchial asthma

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Abstract

Background: Bronchial asthma is a clinical syndrome with possible correlation to medicinal plants in relieving the asthmatic symptoms.

Methods: This study was performed in the Al- Kadhimiya teaching hospital from September 2008 to may 2009 on 62 patients of both sexes who were allocated to six groups plus 15 healthy adults as control. Each group was given one of the following agents: Prednisolone, Fennel, Thyme and combinations of Prednisolone with Fennel or Thyme or Anisum and their pulmonary function tests were conducted as well as measuring the levels of serum electrolytes: Calcium (Ca), Magnesium (Mg), Potassium (K) and Selenium (Se) before and after the treatment.

Results: Most of the tested plants have positive effects on pulmonary function tests with significant increase in values of forced expiratory volume in first second (FEV₁%) and forced volume capacity (FVC) and clinical improvement of patients condition and marked decrease in asthmatic attacks.

Conclusion: Medicinal plants can reduce the symptoms of bronchial asthma and improve pulmonary functions. They are safe, less hazardous and cheap, but may take long time.

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Keywords: Chronic asthma, Medicinal plants, pulmonary function tests, serum electrolytes.

INTRODUCTION

Bronchial asthma is a clinical syndrome of unknown etiology characterized by three distinct components: Recurrent episodes of bronchial obstruction, an exaggerated bronchoconstriction response to stimuli and inflammation of airways with mucosal edema. Both genetic and environmental factors are involved in asthma etiology [1]. Many allergens like air pollutants (ozone and cigarette smoking) infections, exercise and non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs [2],

psychological factors, gastroesophageal reflux and obesity [3] also are involved.

The pathogenesis of chronic bronchial asthma is a complex; it may involve both airway inflammations with an oxidant-antioxidant imbalance [4]. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) have been shown to be associated with asthma pathogenesis by evoking bronchial hyperactivity, stimulating histamine release from the mast cells and mucus secretion from airway epithelial cells [5]. Some medicinal plants such as *Thymus Vulgaris* (Thyme) and *Nigella Sativa* (Black seed) have been shown to inhibit the contraction of the tracheal smooth muscle which is stimulated histamine and acetylcholine in animals [6]. The current study was carried out to explore the effect of some medicinal plants such as *Foeniculum vulgare* (Fennel), *Thymus vulgaris* (Thyme) and *Pimpinella anisum* (Aniseed) in management the patients with chronic bronchial asthma and improvement of their symptoms.

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Subjects and Methods

This study was performed in Al- Kadhimiyia teaching hospital from September 2008 to may 2009. Sixty two adult patients with 15 healthy subjects of both sexes were involved in this study. Their age range was 33-55 years. Patients suffering from any disease other than chronic asthma were excluded. Cigarette smoking, Alcohol consumers and pregnant women also were excluded from the study. The final diagnosis is based on the symptoms and clinical examination. This study was approved by ethical committee of college of medicine. The patients were advised to take special kinds of diet and they were prevented from any exercise or exposure to any allergen.

The patients were randomly allocated to six groups; they were taking the drugs orally.

Group 1 (30 patients): they were given a single dose of Prednisolone 0.15 mg/Kg tablet once daily for interval of one week.

Group 2 (16 patients): they were given thyme 40 mg/Kg in 200 ml of water for two weeks.

Group 3 (16 patients): they were given fennel 40 mg/Kg in 200 ml of water for two weeks.

Group 4 (10 patients): they were given Prednisolone 0.075 mg/Kg once daily plus thyme 14 mg/Kg in 200 ml of water once daily for two weeks.

Group 5 (10 patients): they were given Prednisolone 0.075 mg/Kg once daily plus fennel 14 mg/Kg in 200 ml of water once daily for two weeks.

Group 6 (10 patients): they were given Prednisolone 0.075 mg/Kg once daily plus anisum 50 mg/Kg in 200 ml of water once daily for two weeks.

Plants were identified by Iraqi national center of herbs, all plants were cleaned to remove abnormal materials and selected parts of plants were used; leaves (e.g. thyme), seeds (e.g. fennel and anisum). Plants were crushed and grounded well into powder then mixed with boiled water and covered for 10 minutes then filtered.

Pulmonary function test was performed using a total computerized spirometer (Discom-14, Autospirom chest corporation Tokyo-Japan). The parameters used to assess the severity of asthma in the present study were forced volume capacity FVC and forced expiratory volume in first second FEV₁%.

Blood samples were taken before the patients received any medication and after the improvement of the symptoms. Serum Mg²⁺ and Se²⁺ of all patients were measurement by using GFA-4B graphite tube with auto sample dispenser model 60 G flameless atomic absorption photometer. Serum Ca²⁺ and K⁺ determined by using flame emission spectrophotometry (Gleenhomp).

All data were coded and analyzed using SPSS 10.01 statistical package for social sciences.

RESULTS

In therapy of bronchial asthma drugs and plants have been used either solely or in combination. The results revealed significant increase in FEV₁% and FVC for all the agents used except anisum. The changes in the levels of serum electrolytes also confirming the results. Serum Se of all the groups was significantly elevated at mean time. Serum Mg also significantly elevated with exception of anisum. The serum K was significantly changed in fennel and combination of fennel and thyme with small dose of Prednisolone while serum Ca was significantly raised only with thyme (tables 1, 2and3).

Parameter	Before treatment	After treatment
FEV ₁ %	72.75 ± 5.09	* 78.63 ± 3.34
FVC/L	1.05 ± 0.15	* 2.25 ± 0.16
Ca/mmol/L	1.97 ± 0.07	2.10 ± 0.10
K/mmol/L	3.5 ± 0.24	3.50 ± 0.08
Mg/mmol/L	0.73 ± 0.05	* 0.81 ± 0.15
Se / µg / L	44.62 ± 6.35	* 49.17 ± 4.96

Table (1) The effect of a single dose of Prednisolone (0.15 mg/kg) orally given for one week on pulmonary function parameters and electrolyte serum levels.

*Results were significant at P < 0.05

Parameter	Before treatment	After treatment		
		Fennel	Thyme	Anisum
FEV ₁ %	78.3 ± 3.39	*84.21 ± 2.65	*90.51 ± 4.18	79.26 ± 2.5
FVC/L	2.25 ± 0.16	*3.00 ± 0.03	*3.30 ± 0.07	2.54 ± 0.12
Ca/mmol/L	2.10 ± 0.10	2.36 ± 0.09	2.53 ± 0.08	2.24 ± 0.07
K/mmol/L	3.5 ± 0.08	*3.71 ± 0.14	*3.68 ± 0.11	3.58 ± 0.30
Mg/mmol/L	0.81 ± 0.05	*0.90 ± 0.02	*0.91 ± 0.02	0.85 ± 0.02
Se / µg / L	49.17 ± 4.96	*56.42 ± 2.80	*60.05 ± 6.35	*54.75 ± 3.14

Table (2) The effect of Prednisolone (0.075 mg/Kg) orally given with fennel at concentration (5mg/ml) for 1-2 week or thyme at concentration (5mg/ml) orally for one week or celery at concentration (1g /ml) orally for one week or anisum at concentration (17.5mg/ml) orally for 2 weeks on pulmonary function parameters and electrolyte serum levels.

* Results were significant at P < 0.05

Parameter	Fennel		Thyme	
	Before treatment	After treatment	Before treatment	After treatment
FEV ₁ %	77.41 ± 3.30	*85.50 ± 4.27	67.66 ± 2.71	*83.48 ± 3.35
FVC/L	2.38 ± 0.27	*3.06 ± 0.37	1.03 ± 0.09	*3.25 ± 0.11
Ca/mmol/L	2.06 ± 0.06	2.45 ± 0.15	1.97 ± 0.07	*2.44 ± 0.06
K/mmol/L	3.94 ± 0.05	*3.65 ± 0.12	3.57 ± 0.05	3.60 ± 0.08
Mg/mmol/L	0.78 ± 0.02	0.81 ± 0.04	0.69 ± 0.01	*0.80 ± 0.07
Se / µg / L	54.66 ± 1.30	*61.39 ± 3.16	38.43 ± 0.50	*61.15 ± 3.12

Table (3) The effect of thyme (40 mg/kg) or fennel (40 mg/Kg) orally for two weeks on pulmonary function parameters and serum electrolyte levels.

* Results were significant at P < 0.05

DISCUSSION

Bronchial asthma is an inflammatory syndrome characterized by episodes of acute bronchoconstriction causing shortness of breath, cough, chest tightness, wheezing and rapid respiratory rate [7]. The diagnosis of asthma had been established in each patient and it was based on the symptoms and clinical examination. Prednisolone is well known corticosteroid and was used in group 1 to produce bronchial muscle relaxation but without directly affecting the bronchial muscle. It acts by decreasing the inflammatory cascade, reversing mucosal edema and inhibiting the release of leukotrienes [8].

The effect of thyme (group 2) in relaxation of bronchial muscle may be attributed to flavones present in thyme [9], also to the antioxidant effect of flavonoids that inhibits superoxide formation [10]. These results are compatible to the results obtained by the study that used thyme to produce relaxation in the tracheal smooth muscle of rabbit after contraction by histamine [11]. The relaxant effect of fennel (group 3) is related to its strong antiradical scavenging activity caused by eight antioxidant compounds which present in the seed [12].

The combination of the half dose of Prednisolone with small dose of thyme and fennel (groups 4 and 5) produced relaxation of bronchial muscle and improvement of the symptoms. The serum selenium level of combination of fennel with a half dose of Prednisolone will be higher than using Prednisolone alone in large dose. This effect is due to drug interaction and high antioxidant activity of both drugs.

It is reported that thyme and fennel possess antioxidant activity that cause bronchial muscle relaxation (groups 2, 3, 4 and 5), this result is compatible with that of the study which proved that antioxidant drugs are effective in chronic bronchial asthma [13].

The effect of anisum when used in combination (group 6) showed no significant changes in all the parameters except significant elevation in serum selenium level like other agents. Anisum has expectorant effect with estrogenic activity [14].

In assessment to the changes in levels of serum electrolytes, most of the patients recorded low level of serum calcium; this result is compatible with that of the study that reported no hypocalcaemia in chronic asthma patients [15]. The increased calcium level with thyme may be due to calcium channel

blocking effect which resulted in decreased bronchial muscle tone^[16].

It has been reported that serum magnesium level was decreased producing hypomagnesaemia in patients with chronic bronchial asthma^[17]. This result is compatible with that found in our study before treatment. Hypokalemia was reported in patients with bronchial asthma, potassium efflux lead to bronchial muscle relaxation.

CONCLUSION

Medicinal plants can be used alone or in combination with drugs in management of chronic bronchial asthma and prophylaxis, they are safe, less hazardous and cheap but may take long time.

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Immunohistochemical expression of matrix metalloproteinase -7 (mmp-7) in human colorectal carcinoma using specified automated cellular image analysis system: Clinicopathological study

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Abstract

Objectives: To evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of Matrix Metalloproteinase-7(MMP-7) in colorectal adenocarcinoma and to correlate this immunohistochemical expression with different clinicopathological parameters.

Methods: The study was retrospectively designed. Thirty three paraffin blocks from patients with colorectal adenocarcinoma and 20 samples of non-tumorous colonic tissue were taken as control group were included in the study. Metalloproteinase-7 (MMP-7, Matrilysin) expression was assessed by Immunohistochemistry method. The scoring of immunohistochemical staining was done by a specified automated cellular image analysis system (Digimizer).

Results: The frequency of positive immunohistochemical expression of MMP-7 was significantly higher in carcinoma than control group (87.87% versus 10%) (P-value <0.001). Strong MMP-7 staining was mainly seen in carcinoma cases (39.39%) in comparison with control (0%), the difference is significant ($p < 0.001$). The three digital parameters of MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression (Area (A), Number of objects (N), and intensity (I)) were significantly higher in carcinoma than control. In carcinoma, there was a significant positive correlation between size of tumor and intensity of staining (I) of MMP-7 ($p < 0.05$), also a significant positive correlation of the three digital parameter (A, N, and I) of MMP-7 with grade, stage, lymph node involvement and lymphovascular permeation in colorectal carcinoma was identified ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: MMP-7 may play an essential role in disease progression and lymph node metastasis of colorectal cancer.

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Keywords: Colorectal cancer, MMP-7, Immunohistochemical

INTRODUCTION

Colorectal cancer (CRC) ranks the seventh among the commonest ten cancers in Iraq (Iraqi Cancer Registry, 2005). It is a major public health problem and there is renewed interest in understanding the basic principles of its molecular biology.^[1]

MMP-7 (matrix metalloproteinase-7, matrilysin), a member of MMPs, is thought to be related to progression of many kinds of carcinomas. Previous study suggested that MMP-7 play a more important role in the invasion and progression of tumor than

other MMPs because of its minimum molecular weight (28 kDa) and unique structure.^[2]

During tumor progression, matrilysin is expressed in benign and malignant tumors that arise from the glandular epithelium. Matrilysin has broad substrate specificity against extracellular matrix (ECM) components, including elastin, type IV collagen, fibronectin, vitronectin, aggrecan, and proteoglycans.^[3]

MMP-7, the smallest MMP, appears to be one of the most important MMPs in CRC. It is over-expressed in the majority of CRC, and its expression correlates with progression and hepatic metastasis.^[4] Both MMP-7 mRNA, as determined by qualitative reverse transcriptase-polymerase chain reaction, and MMP-7 protein, as detected by a combination of immunoblotting, zymography, and immunohistochemistry, are consistently expressed in liver metastases. Moreover, immunohistochemistry indicated that MMP-7 was mainly located at the 'growing edge' of the tumor.^[5]

The aim of the present study is to evaluate the immunohistochemical expression of Matrix Metalloproteinase-7(MMP-7) in colorectal

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adenocarcinoma and to correlate this immunohistochemical expression with different clinicopathological parameters "Age and gender of the patients, site, size, macroscopical type, microscopical type, stage and grade, in addition to lymph node status, intratumoral lymphocytic infiltration and lymphovascular permeation".

Methods

The study was retrospectively designed. A total of 53 tissue samples (paraffin block and tissue biopsies) were included in the study.

Out of the total number of tissue samples, 33 paraffin blocks from patients with colorectal carcinomas were collected from Gastroenterology and Hepatology Center, Gastroenterology unit at Al-Kadhmiya Teaching Hospital and private laboratories for the period 2006-2010. The control group included 20 samples of non-tumorous colonic tissue taken from autopsy cases from the Institute of Forensic Medicine. These specimens were processed and paraffin embedded in the same center. The clinicopathological parameters were obtained from patients' admission case sheets and pathology reports.

From each block, 2 sections of 5µm thickness were taken, one section was stained with Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) and slides were revised for the type, grade and stage of colorectal carcinoma (according to Astler-Coller staging system). Additional histopathological features were studied including: intratumoral lymphocytic infiltration and lymphovascular permeation. The other section was stained immunohistochemically using three steps-indirect streptavidin method for Monoclonal Mouse Anti-Human Matrix Metalloproteinase-7 (MMP-7, Matrilysin); clone 3F264, manufactured by US Biological. Brown cytoplasmic and membranous staining is considered positive reaction (figures 1 and 2). Positive control is breast carcinoma tissue. Technical negative control was obtained by omission of primary antibody.

Scoring of immunohistochemical staining

Scoring of immunohistochemical staining was performed using specialized automated cellular image analysis system, Digimizer software, version 3.7.0.

To run the Digimizer program it needs a personal computer (PC) with Windows 2000, Windows XP, Windows Server 2003, Windows Vista and Windows 7, with at least 128 MB RAM and about 8 Megabyte free space on the hard disk.^[6]

Image capture

Using a light microscope (Proway, China), each immunohistochemically stained slide was scanned with 10 × objectives for the positive brown immunostaining and with 40×objective, three fields that reflect the best of the overall immunostaining of the entire slide were chosen and captured using a Sony digital camera (digital still camera DSH-H55). Captured images of 1392×1040 pixels were saved on PC in an uncompressed JPG format.

Image analysis

Each image was analyzed by Digimizer software (Version 3.7.0). The measurements comprised the number of objects per image area that tagged by magic cursor on DAB positive cells, fractional area (in pixels) of these objects and the average intensity of the brown color for the selected objects depending on the expression of the antigens in the cells. The measurements performed on an image were contained in the measurements list window. The integrated statistics window displays summary statistics for the different measurements that are displayed in the measurements list. These include: total number of objects(n), mean of the area of immunostaining, and mean of the average intensity of immunostaining, standard deviation (SD), minimum and maximum values)(Fig.3). Summary statistics were saved as Excel spreadsheet 2007file. The foreword mentioned image analysis was performed for the three images captured for each slide separately and the average of results was taken.

Determination of staining intensity cut-off value

Most of the studies refer to use the intensity of the staining as a tool for classification of immunohistochemical expression of molecular marker into well-defined scores.⁽⁷⁾

The standard quality control lab NordiCQ is a professional and scientific organization independent of economic or political interests, its work is primarily based on routine immunostaining of slides from standard processed human histological specimens with varying expression of antigens. NordiCQ classified the color intensity of DAB positive cells into four categories: strong (+3) for dark brown immunostained slides, moderate (+2) for brown immunostained slides, weak (+1) for light brown to yellow color immunostained slides and negative for non-stained slides.^[8]

To obtain a cut-off value for intensity of immunostaining, photomicrographs presented at the website of NordiCQ showing different grades of

brown color intensity of DAB positive cells :strong ,moderate and weak were analyzed by digimzer software ,and according to this analysis, the digital value of intensity was classed into three categories: weak, moderate and strong, taking into consideration that the digital value of intensity of staining is inversely proportional to digital number in the

digimzer color scale which ranges from 0.000 for the intense black color to 0.999 for the white color (Table 1).^[7]

Grade of intensity	Digital value of digimzer
Strong +3	0.00-0.291
Moderate +2	0.292-0.719
Weak +1	0.720-0.999
Negative	1.000

Table 1. Determination of staining intensity cut-off value^[7]

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using SPSS program (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) version 16 and Microsoft Office Excel 2007. Numeric data were expressed as mean± SEM, frequency was used to express discrete data. ANOVA was used to analyze numeric data while Chi-square was used to analyze discrete data, and benferroni test was used for multiple comparisons.P- Value of less than 0.05 was considered significant. For Digimzer software, the integrated statistics window displays statistics (n, mean, SD, minimum and maximum) of the

measurements in the Measurements list; these measurements were saved as Excel 2007 spreadsheet file.

Results

Clinicopathological parameters

Table 2 shows the clinicopathological parameters studied for colorectal carcinoma patients in this study.

Parameters		Carcinoma (33 cases)
Age	Mean	56.03±2.37 years
	Range	27 - 80 years
Gender	Male	19(57.57%)
	Female	14(42.42%)
	M: F	1.35:1
Site	Right colon	10(30.30%)
	Left colon	23 (69.69%)
Size	Mean	6.46±63 cm
Gross morphology of carcinomas	Fungating	20(60.60%)
	Ulcerative	8(24.24%)
	Annular	5(15.15%)

Histopathological types of carcinomas	Non-Mucinous	25(75.75%)
	Mucinous	8(24.24%)
Grade of carcinoma	Well-differentiated	2 (6.06%)
	Moderately-differentiated	29(87.87%)
	Poorly -differentiated	2 (6.06%)
Stage of carcinoma(Astler-Coller)	B2	20 (60.6%)
	C1	3(9.09%)
	C2	9(27.27%)
	D	1(3.03%)
Lymph node involvement in carcinoma	Positive	13(39.39%)
	Negative	20(60.60%)
Lymphovascular permeation in carcinoma	Positive	29(87.87%)
	Negative	4(12.12%)
Lymphocytic infiltration in carcinoma	Positive	24(72.72)
	Negative	9(27.27%)

Table 2. Clinicopathological parameters of patients studied Comparison of MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression in colorectal carcinoma and control group.

The frequency MMP-7 -positive cases was significantly higher in carcinoma than control group (87.87% versus 10%) (P-value <0.001). The classification of the MMP-7 positive cases of carcinoma and control groups into different grades of intensity (negative, weak, moderate, and strong) according to the tabulated values of NordiCQ laboratories showed that strong MMP-7 staining was

mainly seen in carcinoma cases (13, 39.39%) in comparison with control (0, 0%), the difference is significant (p<0.001) (figures 2 and 3) (table 3).

The three digital parameters of MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression (Area (A), Number of objects (N), and intensity (I)) were significantly higher in carcinoma than control group.

MMP-7 expression		Carcinoma No. (%)	Control No. (%)	p-value
Frequency	Positive	29(87.87%)	2(10%)	<0.001
Intensity of staining	Negative	4(12.12%)	18(90%)	<0.001
	Negative	18(54.54%)	18(90%)	
	Weak	0(0%)	1(5%)	
	Moderate	5(15.15%)	1(5%)	
	Strong	10(30.30%)	0(0%)	

Table 3. Immunohistochemical expression of MMP-7 in patients and control groups.

Correlation of MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression with different clinicopathological parameters studied in patients with colorectal carcinomas.

There was no significant correlation between mean (A, N, and I) of MMP-7 and age, gender, site, gross morphology, histopathological types and lymphocytic infiltration in colorectal carcinoma (p>0.05) (table 4). There was a significant positive correlation between size of tumor and intensity of staining (I) of MMP-7 (p<0.05). There was significant positive correlation

of the three digital parameter (A, N, and I) of MMP-7 with grade, stage, lymph node involvement and lymphovascular permeation in colorectal carcinoma (p<0.05) (table 4).

Parameter	Area (A) (p-value)	No. of objects(N) (p-value)	Intensity(I) (p-value)
Age	0.518	0.695	0.730

Gender	0.701	0.884	0.409
Site	0.146	0.058	0.080
Size	0.619	0.656	0.005
Gross morphology	0.074	0.750	0.171
Histopathological types	0.141	0.258	0.432
Grade	0.014	0.038	0.002
Stage	0.008	0.005	0.034
Lymph node involvement	0.045	0.023	0.028
Lymphovascular permeation	0.004	0.028	0.043
Lymphocytic infiltration	0.675	0.432	0.229

Table 4. Correlation between MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression and different clinicopathological parameters in patients studied.

Discussion

MMPs are over-expressed in a variety of premalignant tumor tissues, including colorectal adenoma and MMP-7 has been shown to be important in the growth of early colonic adenomas and their transformation into invasive cancer⁽⁹⁾.

The present study found that the frequency MMP-7 – positive cases was significantly higher in carcinoma than control group and strong MMP-7 staining was mainly seen in carcinoma cases in comparison with control, the difference is significant. The three digital parameters of MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression (Area (A), Number of objects (N), and intensity (I)) were significantly higher in carcinoma than control group.

Several published studies are in accordance with these data, a study by Rui and Chengwu demonstrated that MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression in colorectal carcinoma was higher than in normal tissues and the difference was significant^[10] Noshio *et al.* also observed a progressive increase in the expression of MMP-7 during the transition from normal to adenomatous to carcinomatous colonic mucosa.^[11] Roca *et al.* found that 49/60 (81.7%) of CRC cases were positive for MMP-7 and that normal colonic epithelium exhibited a weak expression of MMP-7. On the contrary, CRC cases presented a strong cytoplasmic expression.^[12] Duan *et al.* also demonstrated that MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression rate in adenocarcinoma (69.2%) was

significantly higher than that in normal colorectal mucosa (15.0%).^[13]

In the present study, MMP-7 expression in colorectal cancer cells showed diffuse cytoplasmic or membranous staining, which was usually most pronounced at the invasive front of the colorectal cancer. MMP-7 expression was significantly correlated with tumor size, grade, stage, lymph node involvement and lymphovascular permeation. These data tempted us to speculate that MMP-7 facilitates the lymph node metastasis of colorectal cancer and indicate that over-expression of MMP-7 plays an essential role in invasion and metastasis of colorectal cancer.^[4]

Most studies agree with the present one. Kurokawa *et al.* revealed that MMP-7 was significantly correlated with tumor size, grade, depth of invasion, lymphovascular permeation and nodal metastasis.^[14] Rui and Chengwu, demonstrated the of MMP-7 expression that in colorectal cancer showed a positive correlation with lymph node metastasis, Duke's stage and depth of invasion^[10]. Koskensalo *et al.* reported a significant correlation between MMP-7 immunoeexpression and tumor differentiation in colorectal cancer.^[15] Adachi *et al.* and Duan *et al.* showed that MMP-7 protein expression was also associated with Dukes Staging and lymph node status.^[13, 16] Luo *et al.* found that MMP-7 mRNA expression level was correlated with Dukes Staging and histological differentiation grade.^[2]

Al-Tamimi, in Iraq recorded that MMP-7 immunohistochemical expression was correlated with grade of colorectal carcinoma, however, there was non-significant correlation with stage or nodal involvement in discordance to other studies and explained the cause of the difference being attributed to the difference in sample size, type and specificity of the reagents used.^[17]

Cho *et al.* investigated the immunohistochemical expression of MMP-7 in 87 patients with stage II or III rectal carcinoma and demonstrated that MMP-7

expression was found to be significantly correlated with the presence of nodal metastasis ($p=0.029$). No relationship was found between the expression of MMP-7 and age, sex, tumor size, or tumor grade. [18]

Pesta *et al.* found that there were statistically significant differences in the levels of MMP-7 mRNA using reverse transcription real-time PCR between normal colorectal tissue and tumor tissue, but did not find any statistically significant correlation between mRNA level of MMP-7, expression and localization of tumor, clinical stage or course of disease. [19]

The differences in the results are probably caused by the variability in the techniques used for the measurement of MMP-7 activity in colorectal tissue (immunohistochemistry, insitu hybridization, enzyme assay, PCR), different selection criteria of cases, in other words, selecting cases in certain grade or stage, cases with early invasive colorectal carcinomas or with liver or lymph node metastases, different staging systems (Dukes, Astler and Collier or TNM staging systems), different statistical analyses, sample size difference and non-homogenous population.

Compared with the manual immunohistochemical method, there are major benefits of using such an image analyzer (Digimizer) to quantitate immunohistochemical staining. First, it converts a qualitative or semiquantitative assay to a truly quantitative assay. Second, it can improve assay objectivity and reproducibility. Third, such image analyzer-assisted immunohistochemical quantitation does not need much additional training and is simple to perform. Instead of adding a totally new assay to laboratory operation, it modifies only the quantitation step while keeping the previous immunohistochemical assay steps unchanged. However, the implementation of the ACIS system is likely to be an expensive process. In addition, the cost of continuous use and maintenance of such an image analyzer may be substantial. Software and hardware upgrades also may be needed. [20]

In conclusion, MMP-7 expression is significantly higher in carcinoma than control group and might play an essential role in disease progression and lymph node metastasis of colorectal cancer.

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Increased nucleated red blood cells in infants of diabetic mothers

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Abstract

Background: The erythroblasts or normoblast or nucleated red blood cells (NRBC) is an immature form of the red blood cells a precursor of reticulocytes. The aim of the study was to find the normative value of NRBC in healthy term newborns in a sample of Iraqi people and to evaluate NRBC as a marker for chronic intra uterine fetal hypoxia in infants of diabetic mothers.

Patient and method: In this prospective study a cord blood specimens of (130) term newborn were examined for nucleated red blood cell (NRBC) per 100 WBC. The cases divided in to two groups: First group includes (100) newborns of non diabetic mothers. Second group (30) newborns of diabetic mothers.

Results: The mean value of NRBC per 100 WBC in infant of non diabetic mothers (control group) is (2.43). It was found that there is significant increased in mean of NRBC in the group II (infant of diabetic mothers) which is (18.5, $p < 0.0001$).

It was concluded that in infants of diabetic mothers as the chronic intra uterine hypoxia which result from poor maternal glycolic control caused increased placental oxygen consumption & decreased oxygen delivery to fetus & this lead to stimulating the erythropoietin hormone and this presumed to increase the number of NRBC & RBC in peripheral circulation to overcome the intra uterine hypoxia, so NRBC per 100 WBC count in cord blood can be regarded as a good indicator for fetuses prone to such chronic hypoxia

Conclusions: 1- the mean value of nucleated red blood cell (NRBC) per 100 white blood cells in a healthy, term, singleton neonate was (2.43 $\pm$ 2.34). 2- A significant increased number of NRBC in cord blood of infant of diabetic mothers was associated with states of chronic intra uterine hypoxia & the mean value of nucleated red blood cell was (18.5 $\pm$ 7.32).

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Keywords: Nucleated red blood cell, NRBC, Infant of diabetic mother

INTRODUCTION

The erythroblasts or normoblast or nucleated red blood cells (NRBC) is an immature form of the red blood cells a precursor of reticulocytes. The NRBC test was first developed to correct the white blood cells (WBC) count in new born when the

later was done with a coulter counter to eliminate NRBCs a source of error with the automated WBCS count^[1]

The first investigations as to presence of NRBC in the blood of newborn infants are accredited to Neuman in 1871^[2] Loss, Geiss Lee and Gapha in 1895 concluded that normoblasts did not occur in the blood of newborn infants and that their presence therefore, must be considered as pathological sign. The presence of higher NRBC count indicates

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pathology. [3] it was found in prematurity and in pathologic conditions such as erythroblastosis fetalis, congenital heart diseases and still birth [1]. Another reports of increased of NRBC in states of active erythropoiesis resulting from such events as intrauterine hypoxia [4] early gestation hemolysis and fetal blood loss. [5,6]

Later studies demonstrated elevated count in small for gestational age neonates and in cases complicated by maternal diabetes or preeclampsia [7,8]

Recently elevated NRBCs counts have been associated with long-term neurological impairment [7, 8, 9] and with more admission to neonatal intensive care unite. [8]

Hematopoiesis

Regardless of gestational age, anatomic location, production of all hemopoietic tissues begins with pluripotent stem cells that are capable of both self-renewal and clonal maturation into all blood cell lineages. Progenitor cells differentiate under the influence of Colony-Stimulating-factors (CSF), Interleukins (IL), and Thrombopoietin [10]

Erythropoieses

Erythropoieses involves a great variety and number of cells at different stages of maturation, starting with the first stem cell progeny committed to erythroid differentiation ending with the mature circulating red cell. [11,12]

Erythropoietin (EPO) is a glycoprotein that binds to specific receptors on the surface of erythroid precursors; it has been established as the major humeral regulator of red cell production. [12]

Erythropoiesis and hypoxia

The hematopoietic system responds to hypoxia by increasing erythropoietin which increases erythroid production, and releasing less mature forms [1,20], the only known stimulus for erythropoietin is tissue hypoxia, which has been well documented in both human fetal & animal models [12,13,21.]

In cord blood of human infants, increase levels have been reported in conditions associated with intra-uterine hypoxia. Other studies found a

significant association between fetal EPO and erythroblast count. [20]

Infant of diabetic mothers

Both fetal hyperglycemia and hyperinsulinemia cause fetal acidosis and intrauterine hypoxia resulting from poor glycemic control that's associated with maternal hyperglycemia and subsequent fetal hyperglycemia and hyperketonemia [31]

Fetal hypoxemia most likely because increased placenta oxygen consumption and decrease oxygen delivery to fetus and within hours fetal hypoxia stimulates erythropoietin secretion this lead to production of NRBC and increase RBC mass to overcome the intra uterine hypoxia [21]

Aim of the study

- 1- To find the normative value of NRBC in healthy term newborns in a sample of Iraqi people.
- 2- To evaluate NRBC as a marker for chronic intra uterine fetal hypoxia in infants of diabetic mothers.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

Prospective study extended over 5 months (20-3-2007) to (20-8-2007) performed in to delivery rooms and surgical theaters in (al Zahra teaching hospital). (180) live born infants evaluated at delivery they were fulfilled the following general Criteria:-

- 1-singleton
- 2- Term pregnancy (gestational age >37 wk and <42wk) by last menstrual period and 1 or early ultrasound (<20 wk gestational age) ended with uneventful vaginal delivery or elective caesarian section.
- 3- Normal intra partum history (no maternal illness)
- 4- Normal antipartum events
- 5- Clear amniotic fluid
- 6- Apgar score at 1 and 5 minute more than 6
- 7- No neonatal disorder
- 8- Normal neurological evaluation at discharge

9- For all cases mother age ranged between (18-40) years. Parity between (1-4), positive blood group, with no history of hypertension, antipartum hemorrhage, blood disease, smoking, alcohol or drug use.

The cases categorized in to two groups:

Group I infants of non diabetic mothers

Consisted of (140) Samples of healthy newborns and with healthy non diabetic mothers; other maternal illnesses were excluded such as hypertension, blood diseases. Smoking, drugs ;from these samples only (100) samples were fulfilled all general criteria while the reminders (40) samples were discarded .

GroupII infants of diabetic mothers

Consisted of (40) Samples of healthy newborns but of diabetic mothers. Other maternal illnesses were excluded such as hypertension, blood diseases. Smoking, drugs. Only (30) Samples were fulfilled all general criteria while the reminders (10) samples were discarded.

Blood samples from umbilical cord were collected immediately after delivery the blood sample examined for:-

- 1- PCV
- 2- Platelet count
- 3- WBC count & differential count.
- 4- NRBC (per 100 WBC)
- 5- Blood film

RESULTS

The descriptive data of study groups showed in table 1.

Table (1) demographic data of study population

total cases(n=130)	Number	Mean	%
Gestational age (wk)	130	38.2	
Birth weight (gm)	130	3555	
Materna age(yr.)	130	28.3	
Gravity	130		
Primigravida	22		17%
Multigravida	108		83%
Type of delivery	c.s	25	20%
	NVD	105	80.7%
Sex of Newborn	Mal	63	50.7%
	Female	64	49.3%

Group I:-

- The mean value NRBC per /100 WBC of group I population (n=100) is(2.43), SD (0.235)range 0-12 (table 2) the mean gestational age is(38.92) and mean weight is (3725)
- The mean nucleated red blood cell NRBC in healthy newborn population is expected to range between (4.3-5) as showed in table 2

Table (2) description of the control group I

control group (n=100)	Min	Max	Mean	SD	SE
NRBC COUNT PER 100 WBC	0	12	2.4300	2.3495	0.2360
GESTATIONAL age in week	37	41	38.92	0.6917	6.317
weight in gram	2600	4000	3725	0.2176	2.176
Pcv	31.00	67.00	45.200	7.8225	

n= number ,min= minimum ,max= maximum ,SD= standard deviation, SE= standard error

The result of one sample t test of group one control was highly significant ($p < 0.0001$).

Group II:-

The mean value of NRBC per /100 WBC count of group II infant of diabetic mothers (n=30) is (18.5) SD (7.323). ... (Table 3) the mean gestational age is (38.92) wk and means weight is (3385) gm

control group (n=30)	Min	max	Mean	SD	SE
NRBC per / 100 WBC	10	33	18.5	7.32	1.34
gestational age in week	37	39	37.4	0.56	0.10
weight in gram	260 0	400 0	3385	0.38	6.88

Table (3) description of group II

The result of one sample t test of group II infant of diabetic mothers was highly significant ($p < 0.0001$).

The result of a comparison between two means of group I and group II shows that the difference was highly significant ($p < 0.0001$) as in table 4.

	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	Sig. (2- tailed)
Group I	100	2.430 0	2.34953	.23495	0.0001
Group II	30	18.50 00	7.32850	1.33799	0.0001

Table 4 Independent samples t test

DISCUSSION

Nucleated red blood cells are rarely found in concentrations higher than 10 per 100 WBC in peripheral blood of healthy term newborn infants.⁽⁹⁾ Previous studies reported an association between increased nucleated red blood cells in peripheral

blood of neonates and intra uterine hypoxemia as in infant of diabetic mothers. [2,7]

Group I:-

100 Normal newborns of healthy non-diabetic mothers with body weight >2500gm & >37 WK (G.A). The mean NRBC is (2.43), compared with other studies reporting normative NRBC data from cord blood, our studies reporting normative results which was relatively accepted compared with other studies.

Group II:-

30 infant of diabetic mothers, body weight >2500gm, full term.

Erythroblastemia:-There was significantly increased NRBC in the cord blood at delivery, mean NRBC is (18.5, $p < 0.0001$) this result is with agreement with previous studies, which found that the NRBC count of infant of diabetic mother were considerably higher at birth.^(4,7)

It is presumed that the increased numbers of NRBC in the peripheral blood reflect increased hematopoiesis or premature release of these cells in response to increased erythropoietin [20] which associated with intra uterine hypoxia. It has been further postulated that appearance of NRBC in peripheral blood indicates extramedullary (mostly hepatic) hematopoietic.^[9]

Conclusions

- 1- The mean value of nucleated red blood cell (NRBC) per 100 white blood cells in a healthy, term, singleton neonate was (2.43 ± 2.34) .
- 2- A significant increased number of NRBC in cord blood of infant of diabetic mothers was associated with states of chronic intra uterine hypoxia & the mean value of nucleated red blood cell was (18.5 ± 7.32) .

Recommendations

An increased NRBC count can be considered as a potentially useful indicator in detecting chronic intra uterine hypoxia as in infant of diabetic mothers and this could be useful factor to determine further

management and admission to neonatal intensive unit.

NRBC count is easy test to apply since the cord blood specimen can be analyzed by equipment readily available in most hospital laboratories.

NRBC count could be put in scoring system including the Doppler ultrasonography of umbilical vessels and placental histopathology for determining a normal growth in infant of diabetic mothers.

More advance studies for emphasizing the theory of hematopoietic shifting using the humeral and other regulating factor are recommended

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Early detection of neonatal deafness by oto-acoustic emission

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Abstract

Background: Hearing loss is one of common birth defect, 2 -6 / 1000 newborn have hearing loss, many of these cases go undetected until third year of life, they miss out vital sound and information in the most critical time of speech and language development which causes significant delays.

Without early detection and intervention, hearing impaired children may suffer cognitive, emotional and psychological delays.

Hearing screening is simple, quick, safe and non invasive, in fact most babies sleep throughout the test.

Objectives: To test the feasibility of implementing Automated Otoacoustic Emission (AOAE) screening for bilateral congenital deafness in neonate.

We report here our experience of using the AOAE test and its performance in a group of 291 babies.

Methods: 291 newborn babies were screened through Automated Otoacoustic emission (AOAE) in Al kadhimiya teaching hospital. The result was considered normal when the newborns showed positive evoked Otoacoustic emission response (Pass sign), those who showed no response (refer sign) were retested after 2 -3 weeks , if they continued to show refer sign they were sent for automated auditory brainstem response (AABR) .

The target condition to be screened for was bilateral sensori-neural hearing impairment of moderate to profound grade (i.e. greater than 40 dB hearing loss).

Results: Of the 291 babies who enrolled in the program, 260 (89.3%) passed the 1st AOAE test. Of 291 tested 31 babies failed in the 1st AOAE test, 6 babies only did not retested, 25 babies return for the 2nd AOAE test and 13 of them passed (52%). Twelve babies failed the screening and required referrals for further audio logical evaluation. The screen-refer rate was 4.1%.

Conclusions: It is essential for all newborns especially those with associated risk factors should undergo hearing screening with AOAE for early diagnosis of neonatal deafness.

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Keywords: Otoacoustic Emission, deafness

INTRODUCTION

Bilateral permanent childhood hearing impairment (PCHI) is an important health problem because of its adverse effect on a child's language and communication skills, social and emotional development and educational achievement [1]. 2 -6 / 1000 newborn have hearing loss [2]. Hearing loss is one of common birth defect with incidence higher than other all congenital defect combined including Cystic fibrosis and Hypothyroidism [3]. It is believed that the first six months of life is the critical period for language skill

acquisition [4]. Initial evidence; have showed that early identification and intervention prior to the age of 6 months are decisive factors in the development and prognosis of these children [5].

Oto acoustic emissions (OAEs) are sounds generated by outer hair cells housed in the cochlea and can be measured in the external ear canal. Detection of OAEs can be hampered by obstructions in the external ear canal and middle ear.

Detectable OAEs, therefore, reflect normal function of the auditory pathway as far as the level of the outer hair cells of the cochlea. This technology can be used to detect sensory hearing loss but not retro-cochlea neural dysfunctions [6].

To date, more than half of the states in the USA have

though the infant DT (Distraction test) has been used for hearing screening since the 1940s, the Department of Health has recently decided to pilot the implementation of universal newborn hearing screening. [8, 9].

- *History of congenital deafness
- *Consanguinity
- *Drug history during pregnancy
- *Family history of congenital anomalies
- *Ototoxic medications

Method

The Instrument

The instrument used was the accuscreen portable OAE machine with a default screening protocol. It produced Transient evoked Otoacoustic emission (TEOAEs). After testing, the result of "Pass"/"Refer" would be displayed according to its pre-programmed pass/ fail criteria. No interpretation of test results by the tester was required.

The Protocol

Figure 1 outlines the protocol for the AOAE screening project.

An observational cross-sectional study was conducted for 291 babies in Al kadhimiya teaching hospital. All babies admitted to the neonatal care unit (babies with risk factors) were tested, while those born in obstetric ward the test was optional.

The test was performed in a silent room, with the child in a state of natural sleep in a common crib.

Two strategies were built in the protocol to minimize false-positive results.

First, we recommended no AOAE testing before the age of 2 weeks. This was to avoid performing the test in very young babies who tended to have unresolved fluid in the middle ears or debris in their ear canals, resulting in undetectable OAE.

Second, we adopted a two-stage screening protocol that only babies who had failed both the 1st and the 2nd AOAE tests would be referred for AABR to confirm the hearing loss. The 2nd AOAE test was performed at least 2 weeks after the 1st AOAE test. AOAE test was not performed in babies older than 3 months of age. This was essentially a practical consideration since older babies could not be settled easily

After the test, a pre-coded card was filled out, using data from the newborns case history record. The population was characterized as follows:

*Age*Sex

*Type of delivery: NVD , CS

*Term: Full term , Preterm (in months)

*History of asphyxia, prolong labor , hyperbilirubinemia

*Mother blood group

*Visible malformations

*Medical history during pregnancy (DM, HT, Infectious dis.)

Figure (1) Protocol of AOAE screening project.

The Procedure

The tests were performed in a silent room, each AOAE test consisted of testing both ears. A "passed" AOAE test result would mean that the baby had passed the test in one or both ears while a "Failed" AOAE test result might mean that the baby had failed the test in either ears or that he/she had failed to complete the test.

If a baby had failed the 1st AOAE test, a 2nd test would be arranged. A baby would only be referred for further diagnostic evaluation if both tests had been failed.

Results

Program Uptake and Completion-rate

Of 291 tested babies, 260 (89.3%) passed the 1st AOAE test. 31 babies failed in the 1st AOAE test, 25 babies return for the 2nd AOAE test, 6 babies only did not retested. Thus over 98 % of the babies who enrolled in the programme had completed the screening. (Figure 2)

(Figure 2)

Repeat and Refer Rates

Twenty-five babies then went on to receive a repeat test and 13 of them passed (52%).

Twelve babies failed the second screening test and required referrals for diagnostic audiological evaluation. (Figure 3)

The screen-refer rate was 4.1%.

(Figure 3)

Programme Yield

While 12 babies were referred out after completing the screening for ABR test.

10 babies (83.3%) did turn up for diagnostic evaluation. After the initial audiological assessment, 3 babies (25%) were confirmed to be normal; while 7 babies were confirmed to have sensori-neural deafness, giving a yield of 2.4 per 100 babies screened, while 2 babies did not return. (Figure 4)

Further Diagnostic Evaluation (ABR test)

(Figure 4)

Of 291 babies enrolled in screening programme 8 (2.7 %) babies have positive family history, 2 of them show refer sign in AOAE test according to the analysis, the main characteristics of the group of children at greater risk of presenting with impaired hearing screening were as follows: family history of congenital hearing loss; craniofacial malformation; meningitis and Consanguinity. (Table1).

Variable	Number	Normal	Impaired
Family history	8	6	2
Consanguinity	25	23	2
Visible anomalies	10	9	1
Asphyxia	5	5	0
Meningitis	4	3	1
CS	176	171	5
NVD	115	113	2
Male	134	130	4
Female	157	154	3
Maternal Smoking	12	12	0
Hyperbilirubinemia	10	10	0

In Figure 5 show the Summary of AOAE screening results.

Figure 5 Summary of AOAE screening result.

Discussion

The aim of this pilot project was to explore the feasibility of implementing AOAЕ in screening programme for detection of neonatal deafness in Iraq. Joint Committee on Infant Hearing had recommended certain benchmarks for an effective universal newborn hearing screening [10], including an uptake of 95% or greater, return-for-follow-up of 75% or higher and screen-refer of less than 4%.

Programme Uptake and Completion-rate

For a universal newborn hearing screening programme to effectively detect PCHI, which is an uncommon condition in the general newborn population, a high programme uptake, say up to 95%, is required [10]. We can increase the uptake of this screening programme by conducting screening in Delivery units in hospitals and also in maternal and child health care centers, and making it mandatory to all newborn babies just like immunization programme. The return-for-2nd AOAЕ test rate of 80.6% and screen completion rate of 98% are remarkably high.

Repeat and Refer Rates

Less than 10.7% of babies tested required a repeat test. Similar results could be found in other screening programmes. A repeat test for babies who have failed the initial test helped to reduce the refer rate to 4.1%, which meets the recommended benchmark of 4% or less [10]. The two-stage protocol is thus important to minimize false positive results and reduce the number of referrals.

Programme Yield

The yield of universal newborn hearing screening has been estimated to be 3 per 1000 babies screened, and 2 - 4 out of every 100 newborn leaving the neonatal intensive care unit [11]. In low risk population it has been estimated to be 0.36 - 0.49 per 1000 babies screened [1]. In Germany 5% of children have impaired ABR (2% bilaterally), in Brazil a universal screening study with Evoked Otoacoustic emission show confirmed hearing loss in 2-3/1000 newborns.

The data in our study show variable result, the prevalence we observed is little above the average, which may be related to characteristic of the present group (newborn in neonatal care unit and those born in Obstetrics unit at a university hospital that is a regional excellence center and therefore provides care to highly complex cases.

Thus a high prevalence of hearing loss in the population treated in this facility can be expected.

The data in our study show that positive family history of congenital hearing loss is a factor significantly associated with hearing impairment.

Other variables associated with the result of neonatal hearing screening are shown table (1).

Limitations of AOAЕ Screening

When applied to the newborn, the AOAЕ technique has two major limitations.

Firstly, it assesses the hearing pathway as far as the cochlea and any retro-cochlear pathology will be missed. However, retro-cochlear pathologies are expected to be rare in the low-risk babies.

Moreover, the prevalence, natural history and optimal mode of management of auditory neuropathies are unknown and therefore the benefit of early detection is uncertain. We therefore consider the AOAЕ technique adequate for routine use in the MCHC (Maternity and child health center) population.

Secondly, the test results depend on the status of the external and middle ears [12]. By avoiding the early neonatal period when test results are frequently affected by the presence of debris in the external ear canal and fluid in the middle ear, and by using a two stages.

AOAЕ/ AOAЕ protocol, we were able to keep the repeat and referral rates at reasonable levels.

Practical Issues

When the test performed in the rooms were not sound treated, despite the sealing effect of an appropriately-sized earpiece, it was found that the tests were often affected by ambient noises such as those arise in from a crowded waiting hall or the public announcement system. As a result, longer testing time might be required.

The age and state (of being quiet or restless) of the baby at testing and baby-handling skills of testers might also affect test results [12, 13]. The study shows that the optimal age for testing was around 21 days and they found that older babies tended to be easily aroused and have more movements. With a total of 291 tests performed, only 11% (n=35) of tests repeated more than three times to be completed. This probably reflected the amount of effort taken to prepare babies for the test and the

Competence of the testers in handling babies.

Conclusion

AOAЕ test is an objective, valid and easy-to-use hearing screening tool. It can be performed by enrolled nurses after brief training. This project showed that hearing screening by AOAЕ yielded good results in terms Of lower repeat and refers rates as well as a higher yield of the target condition. Moreover, the AOAЕ programme met recommended benchmarks on refer rate and return for-follow-up for universal hearing screening. Rolling out the AOAЕ screening to all

Maternity units in hospitals and MCHCs (Maternity and child health centers) will benefit the majority of babies Iraq.

Recommendations

- AOA screening is a promising tool for universal infant hearing screening in Iraq.
- The screening programme should be performed in the maternity units in hospitals and also in the Maternity and child health care units for those delivered at home.
- The test should be mandatory like the immunization programme.
- The best device for this purpose should include the option of ABR.

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Cardiac patients' level of satisfaction with the information given before discharge by nurses in universiti kebangsaan Malaysia medical centre Kuala Lumpur

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Abstract

Background and Objective: Information giving and patient education before discharge of cardiac patients has become a very important activity in the nursing care service. It was found that cardiac patients are not satisfied with the information given most of the time.

The objective of this study was to identify cardiac patients' level of satisfaction regarding information given by nurses before discharge.

Patient and Method: An explorative cross-sectional study was conducted on 61 cardiac patients from January to May 2009 using convenience sampling method. Data were collected using the Patient Continuity of Care Questionnaire (PCCQ). Cronbach's alpha for the PCCQ was 0.88.

Results: More than 90% of the respondents (n=55) were not satisfied with the information given with regards to patient resources, support and educational materials and over 30% were not satisfied with the information given about medication, prognosis, non-urgent symptoms and how to cope and medical supplies. There was a significant relationship between age and cardiac patients' satisfaction ($p=0.011$) where the younger patients scored better satisfaction level.

Conclusion: It can be concluded from the above result that cardiac patients' are not satisfied with the information given by nurses before discharge from hospital.

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Keywords: Cardiac patients, satisfaction, information, discharge, nurses

INTRODUCTION

Caring for cardiovascular disease patients present as one of the greatest challenge for the nursing work force. In Malaysia, cardiovascular disease is one of the top killers where 16.5% of the 45,936 deaths in 2008 were due to heart disease. Heart attack hits Malaysians as early as fifty years old. It is also the main cause of death among women accounting for about 25% of all female deaths in the government hospitals^[1].

Many surviving patients of cardiac diseases have to adapt to living with it, therefore, patient education and information giving has become a very important activity in the nursing care service. Many

prevention programs were established to build awareness among the people by the Ministry of Health to educate the Malaysian population on prevention measures and healthy lifestyle against cardiac diseases. Healthcare providers also create awareness by giving health education pre-hospitalization, during hospitalization and post-hospitalization to provide continuity of care to patients and their family. To ensure that the patients' information have been met adequately prior to discharge sets the stage for a successful self-management and recovery at home^[2]. The main goal of providing information to patients is to increase the understanding about their illness and to promote healthy behaviors among patients with cardiac diseases^[3]. But patients who felt that they have not received adequate information express their dissatisfaction towards the teaching and information giving sessions prior to discharge and post-discharge. These problems are often due to having unmet informational needs^[4].

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It was also found that cardiac patients are often least satisfied with the information that they have received regarding medication, possible future problems, sexual activity, employment and lifestyle. Most of the information they received were on medical and physical aspects [5]. In certain areas, nurses too may not have delivered the necessary information appropriately or patients may not have paid attention due to their illness state and because of this patients may have felt difficulty in understanding and coping during the information giving session. It was found that patients who are discharged with unmet informational needs are at a higher risk for post-hospital complications, readmissions and decreased satisfaction with care. [6,7]

Therefore it is very important that informational needs prior to discharge of cardiac patients must be identified, planned, and provided appropriately according to the patients needs and level of understanding so as to ensure their satisfaction, reduce their post hospitalization risks and ensure compliance to treatment post discharge.

Thus, keeping in mind the importance of information to cardiac patients, the main aim of this study was to determine the level of cardiac patients' satisfaction with the information given by nurses according to socio-demographic data prior to discharge in Universiti Kebangsaan Malaysia Medical Centre (UKMMC). It was also to determine the relationship between the length of hospital stay and level of education with information given by nurses before discharge.

METHOD

This was an explorative cross-sectional study carried out in UKMMC to identify the level of cardiac patients' satisfaction on information given by nurses before discharge from hospital. It was carried out between January and May 2009 after obtaining ethical clearance from the Research Ethics Committee of UKMMC. A total of 61 patients had participated voluntarily in this study. Data was collected using the Patient Continuity of Care Questionnaire (PCCQ) by Hadjistavropoulos et al. [8] which was modified and translated to suit the Malaysian culture. The reliability analysis for the PCCQ using Cronbach alpha was 0.88. A pilot study was carried out to ensure that patients were able to understand and answer all the questions without any problems. The

PCCQ consisted of 27 items which was rated with a Likert scale. The scores were measured with a 4-point scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (1=Strongly disagree; 2=Disagree; 3=Agree and 4=Strongly agree). Data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 12.0 in the form of frequencies, percentages, t-test and ANOVA.

RESULTS

The respondents (n=61) who had volunteered to participate in this study comprised of 30(49%) male patients and 31(51%) female patients. The patients were selected from the Medical, Surgical and Coronary Rehabilitation Wards (CRW). There were 41(67.21%) patients from the medical wards, 8(13.2%) from the surgical wards and 12(19.67%) from CRW. According to the age category, 27(44.3%) of the respondents ranged between 60 to 74 years, 22(36.0%) were <59 years and 12(19.7%) were >75 years.

According to the level of education, 11(18.03%) did not attend school at all, 15(24.59%) had primary school education, 25(40.98%) had secondary school education, 7(11.49%) were from diploma level and 3(4.92%) were from the degree level. According to the length of hospital stay, 39(63.93%) patients were hospitalized between 3-7 days, 19(31.15%) between 8-14 days and 3(4.92%) patients were hospitalized for >15 days.

According to the PCCQ items (Figure 1), the result revealed that more than 90% of the respondents were not satisfied with the information given regarding patient resources, support services and education materials. More than 30% of these patients reported that they were not satisfied with the information given about prognosis, non-urgent symptoms and coping, medication and medical supplies. About 30% of the respondents were also not satisfied with the provision of emotional support and the preparation for discharge.

There was a significant relationship between age and the level of satisfaction ($p=0.011$) on the information given before discharge. In this study it was noted that the younger patients scored better satisfaction level compared to older patients.

Variables	Frequency (%)
Sex	
Male	30(49)
Female	31(51)
Age	
<59	22(36.0)
60-74	27(44.3)
>75	12(19.7)
Marital Status	
Single	1(1.6)
Married	55(90.2)
Others	5(8.2)
Race	
Malay	31(50.8)
Chinese	21(34.4)
Indian	6(9.8)
Others	3(4.9)
Level of Education	
None	11(18.03)
Primary School	15(24.59)
Secondary School	25(40.98)
Diploma	7(11.48)
Degree	3(4.92)
Occupation	
Self Employed	11(18.0)
Unemployed	28(45.9)
Private	5(8.2)
Government	10(16.4)
Others	7(11.5)
Types of Admission	
Medical Wards	41(67.21)
Surgical Wards	8(13.12)
CRW	12(19.67)
Length of Stay	
3-7 days	39(63.93)
8-14 days	19(31.15)
>15 days	3(4.92)

Table (1): Frequency and Percentages of Demographic Variables of Respondents

There was no significant relationship between the length of hospital stay and information given before discharge and the level of education with the information given before discharge.

DISCUSSION

The result revealed that there were many items in the PCCQ which scored higher percentage of dissatisfaction in the information given to cardiac patients by nurses. Information regarding support services, patient resources and support, education materials and self management tools revealed more than 90% of patient dissatisfaction. This supports a

previous study carried out by using the PCCQ in medical and orthopedic areas which had showed similar results, that is, more than 50% of the patients were dissatisfied with the information given by nurses on patient resources, support and educational materials^[8]. One interpretation of the findings in this study is that nurses still lacked skills in assessment of the needs of patients in view of information and did not target at the discharge teaching to ensure that the individual needs of patients were met thus increasing the dissatisfaction of patients.

Figure (1): Mean and Percentage of patients dissatisfied with information given by nurses according to PCCQ items (n=61)

The respondents were not satisfied with information on non urgent symptom and how to cope, on urgent symptoms and whom to contact and about restriction of activities and not satisfied with information on clinical findings that may impact health status. These findings support an earlier study [9] where 6 important issues in discharge planning and teaching were not satisfactorily addressed by healthcare professionals. These were, ways to relieve chest pain, shortness of breath, the resumption of physical activities, stress management, signs and symptoms to monitor at home, what to do if symptoms reappeared and explanation given to family about what to do and who to contact during emergency. The findings in the current study suggest that nurses must be aware of all the crucial information that is required by cardiac patients and must always plan their teaching or information

giving session so as to ensure that all the important information is included in their information giving session.

In the current study, it was found that 36.1% of the respondents were not satisfied with the information about their prognosis and medication. These findings were similar to another study [5] where the relationship between information received and satisfaction with health care post Acute Myocardial Infarction was explored. Here too it was found that the patients were least satisfied with information about medication and possible future problems. These areas were identified as areas with great potential for improvement. [5] Patients expect healthcare professionals to provide all the necessary information as a routine aspect during their stay in the hospital and before discharge. Findings in the current study showed that the nurses provided

information which they perceived to be important to cardiac patients rather than to assess which information that patients perceived to be important which may be the reasons why patients were not satisfied with the information given.

The readiness of cardiac patients to be discharged from the hospital showed a dissatisfaction level of 36.1% and 37.7% were not satisfied with the emotional support given to them. These findings contradicted another study [8] which found that only 9.8% of the respondents were not ready for discharge and 12.8% were dissatisfied with the emotional support provided. Several reasons may explain why this is so with the current study. Patients may have felt that the information received was insufficient thus making them not ready for discharge. Lack of caring behaviors and a busy working schedule, with no time to spare on these activities, on the part of nurses may also have resulted in poor emotional support for these cardiac patients.

The current study found that there was a significant difference between age and level of satisfaction ($p=0.011$) on information given before discharge. This result was similar to an earlier finding [10] which found that younger patients place more importance on health information compared to older adults and collected most of the information during their stay and before discharge. The result showed that there was no relationship between length of hospital stay and cardiac patients' satisfaction ($p=0.312$) and level of education and

cardiac patients' satisfaction ($p=0.684$) on information given before discharge.

CONCLUSION

The findings of this study confirm that there are certain areas where cardiac patients are still not satisfied with the information given to them by nurses before discharge. This is an indication for nurses to be more alert when giving information to these patients. Nurses should assess the patients and their needs before giving the information to ensure that all aspects of care have been included before delivering the information to cardiac patients. Nurses should also upkeep their knowledge so as to provide the information confidently to patients and make them understand what is being said. They should also allow space for the patients to ask questions and probe when patients looked confused or show poor understanding of the information delivered.

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Surgical treatment of perforated typhoid ulcer

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Abstract

Background: Typhoid fever, also known as enteric fever, is caused primarily by *Salmonella typhi* (*S. typhi*). The protean manifestations of typhoid fever make this disease a true diagnostic challenge. The classic presentation includes fever, malaise, diffuse abdominal pain, and constipation. Untreated, typhoid fever is a grueling illness that may progress to delirium, obtundation, intestinal hemorrhage and bowel perforation. The most serious complication of typhoid fever — intestinal bleeding or perforation — may develop in the third week of illness. Frequency of perforation varies between 0.8% and 18%. Intestinal bleeding is often marked by a sudden drop in blood pressure and shock, followed by the appearance of blood in stool. A perforated intestine occurs, causing intestinal contents to leak into abdominal cavity and triggering signs and symptoms such as severe abdominal pain, nausea, vomiting and sepsis. This life-threatening emergency requires immediate medical care.

Patients and methods: The outcome of 21 surgically-treated patients with typhoid ulcer perforation was reported. The patients were admitted as cases with "acute abdomen" during the period February 2003 and December 2010. There were 18 males and 3 females with average age 32 years (range 16 -55). Two types of surgery were used; resection with end to end anastomosis (n=12=57.14%) and debridement, primary closure with ileostomy (n=9=42.85%).

Results: Although resection with anastomosis is more extensive surgery than closure and ileostomy, there was no deference in mortality and morbidity between the two groups.

Conclusions: We recommend the use of resection and anastomosis in treatment of perforated typhoid ulcer when circumstances permit.

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Keywords: Typhoid fever, Typhoid ulcer, Perforation, Surgical treatment.

INTRODUCTION

Typhoid fever, a febrile disease caused by *S. typhi*, a Gram-negative bacillus, is an important problem in tropical countries [1,2,3]. It is generally transmitted by fecal-oral route [1]. In regions of improper and inadequate infrastructure an epidemic may be issued [4]. The most common complications are bleeding and intestinal perforation which continues to be a cause of high morbidity and mortality [3]. Bleeding and perforation usually occur at terminal ileum due to necrosis of Payer's patches

at 2-3 week after the onset of the illness. Perioperative mortality in Typhoid Intestinal Perforation (TIP) may reach up to 80%, especially in patients received surgery due to late perforation [3, 7-9]. In a study including 229 cases, Asefa found TIPs as one of the important causes underlying the acute abdomen¹¹. Preoperative resuscitation, early surgery and post operative intensive care are the milestones in cases of TIPs. The aim of this study to is review TIP cases and evaluate the outcome of two different surgical procedures, resection with end-end anastomosis (n=12) and debridement, primary closure with ileostomy (n=9). The study is a retrospective. The surgical procedures were done by both specialist surgeons and juniors supervised by specialists in Al-Shaheed Alsadr Hospital and Al-

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Al-Kindy Teaching Hospital during the period Feb 2003- Dec 2010.

Patients and Methods

The study included 21 patients as cases of "acute abdomen". Fifteen of the patients were diagnosed as having an "intra-abdominal perforated viscus". The remaining cases (n=6=28.57%) were referred from medical department, as cases of typhoid fever, who deteriorate or developed "abdominal signs", during treatment for typhoid fever. All patients were explored in Al-Shaheed Alsadr Hospital and Al-Kindy Teaching Hospital during the period from February 2003 to December 2010. They were found to have perforations in terminal ileum. The cases were evaluated as regard to age, sex, and period before surgical exploration, site, number and size of perforations, type of surgery performed, mortality and morbidity. The patients were diagnosed to have "acute abdomen" by taking history and performing full physical examination. They were subjected to erect posterior-anterior chest and erect abdominal films, white blood cells count and urinalysis. Patients were neither subjected to focused assessment sonography in trauma (FAST) nor to diagnostic peritoneal lavage (DPL).

Results

There were 21 patients, 18 of them were males (85.7%) and 3 were females (14.3%). The average age was 32 years (range 16-55). Common clinical features were abdominal pain, fever, anorexia, nausea and vomiting. On examinations physical signs were generalized abdominal tenderness, paleness and all signs of generalized peritonitis. The patients were stabilized preoperatively with intravenous fluids and any electrolytes imbalance was corrected; we also start antibiotics (Cefotaxim 1gm twice daily intravenously (I.V.) with I.V. Metronidazole three times daily); All patients were explored via a middle midline incision curved around the right side of the umbilicus, with the opinion that it can be extended upwards or downwards if such extension was needed during laparotomy. Nineteen patients were found to have single perforation of average size of (0.5-1.2) cm with acute inflammatory process around them. Two patients had 2 small perforations nearby. The perforations were located at an average of 50cm from ileocecal valve. Three factors determined the type of the surgical procedure; these are (the condition of the patient, the surgeon's experience and preference and the degree of peritoneal contamination). Surgical resection of ulcer with 2-layered end-end anastomosis (G-1) was performed in 12 patients (57.14%), while debridement, primary closure with ileostomy (G-2) was performed in 9 patients (42.86%). One drain was inserted towards the pelvis in 19 cases, while 2 drains were inserted in 2 cases one near the anastomosis site and one towards the pelvis. The results are summarized in table 1.

Surgical procedure	no. of patients	% of total
Resection with end to end anastomosis	12	57.14%
debridement with closure and ileostomy	9	42.86%

Table 1 summary of surgical procedures

One patient, from the resection group [G-1] (4.76%) aged 55 years developed bilateral well demarcated feet color changes that progressed to gangrene and he died in 3rd postoperative day. Four patients, 2 from each group (G-1, G-2) developed wound infection (19.04%). One patient (4.76%) from the

ileostomy group (G-2) developed wound dehiscence, to whom tension sutures were done, see table 2.

Type of complication	no. of patients	type of surgery	% of total
Wound infection	2	G-1	9.52%
Wound infection	2	G-2	9.52%
Feet gangrene	1	G-1	4.76%
Wound dehiscence	1	G-2	4.76%

G1= resection of ulcer + end-end anastomosis
G2= debridement + closure of ulcer + ileostomy

Table 2 summary of complications in the study group

	No. of patients	type of surgery	% of total
Morbidity	2	G-1	9.52%
	3	G-2	14.29%
Mortality	1	G-1	4.76%

Table 3 Morbidity and Mortality in study group

Discussion

In our study 21 patients treated surgically for perforated typhoid ulcer were evaluated. The common surgical procedure performed was resection of ulcer with end-end anastomosis (n=12= 57.14%). The rest of patients were treated by debridement, closure of perforation with ileostomy (n=9=42.86%).

Bleeding intestinal perforation are the most fatal complications. These complications usually occur 2-3 weeks after the onset of the disease, due to necrosis of Payer's patches. The frequency of perforation is reported to vary between 0.8%-39% depending on the geographic region and its health standers [8, 10]. Butler [12] reviewed 15980 typhoid fever cases from the world literature and found the frequency of perforation to be 2.8%. Hosoglu et al [5] reported the frequency of TIP as 10.5%. In Iraq there are no exact statistical figures for the frequency of perforation. All perforations that we have seen were in terminal ileum, but it was reported in other rare sites, like jejunum and cecum [1, 10]. A case report of perforation in appendicitis was described [12]. In our patients 19 were found to have single perforation of average size of (0.5-1.2) cm with acute inflammatory process around them. Two patients had 2 small perforations nearby. The perforations were in terminal ileum on anti-mesenteric margin, an average

of 50cm from ileocecal valve. It seems that typhoid ulcers do not cause symptoms until they perforate. Perforation will cause peritoneal irritation with abdominal pain, fever and guarding on physical examination. All our patients presented with all these symptoms and signs. None of our patients was complaining of intestinal bleeding. Although relative bradycardia is an important finding in typhoid fever, in our series none of our patients displayed this sign. This may be due to the fact that our patients presented with fever and abdominal pain which elevate the heart rate. Hepatosplenomegaly, which is a frequent finding in typhoid fever, was not found in our series. More than 50% of patients are in their 2nd and 3rd decades. In our series age range was 16-55 years (average 32 years). Men are affected three times more than females [8, 10]. In our patients men were affected 6 times more than females.

Early surgical interference is the optimal treatment option for perforation. However, the type of surgery to be applied is controversial. The surgical options are shown in figure-1.

In our study two options were used, segmental resection with end to end anastomosis and debridement with primary closure and ileostomy.

The most common complication of typhoid ulcer perforation cases is wound infection, while the most serious is formation of a fecal fistula. Wound

dehiscence, intestinal obstruction, intra-abdominal abscess, empyema, bleeding diathesis, and psychosis may occur [8].

In our series there were 3 morbidities in the perforation closure and ileostomy group (33.33%). In resection and end to end anastomosis group there were 2 morbidities (16.67%) and 1 mortality (8.33%). The mortality rate in typhoid perforation cases is reported to vary between 5% and 60% [8,10,29].

Figure-1 Surgical options used in treatment of perforated typhoid ulcer

- Segmental resection + anastomosis
 - Debridement + 2-layered primary repair
 - 2-layered primary repair + end ileostomy
 - Segmental resection + anastomosis followed by an end ileostomy
 - Segmental resection + end ileostomy with mucous fistula
-

CONCLUSION

The treatment of TIP consists of effective resuscitation in the preoperative period, appropriate early surgical intervention, postoperative care, and use of proper antibiotics. Although primary closure of ulcer with ileostomy is the most frequently recommended procedure, ileostomy is associated with high mortality and morbidity. Resection and end to-end anastomosis has low mortality and morbidity rates. Thus resection-anastomosis procedure is recommended as 1st option in treatment of perforated typhoid ulcer. Nevertheless ileostomy may be life saving in severe peritoneal contamination.

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Effectiveness of clinical examination in the detection of early breast malignancy in women with breast mass in comparison with fine needle aspiration(FNA) and histopathology

Nashwan K Mahjob *

Abstract

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of clinical examination in the diagnosis of early breast cancer in women presented with breast mass in comparison with fine needle aspiration cytology study using the histopathological assessment as the gold standard for evaluation of the effectiveness and comparison.

Design: A prospective study.

Setting: Al-Jamhori Teaching Hospital in Mosul, during the period from 1st Jan 2007 to 31st Dec 2010.

Participants: Ninety two patients presented with breast mass, 7 patients showed advanced malignancy, 5 patients refused surgical interference; both groups were excluded from the study. The remaining 80 patients with breast mass were assessed and evaluated.

Main outcome measures: The clinical examination included history of first appearance or discovering of the mass, age, positive family history of malignant breast disease, history of breast trauma, menstrual history, marital state, and number of children, breast feeding and the use of contraceptive pills. Local examination included the site, size, consistency and mobility of the mass, nipple discharge, nipple retraction and the state of axillary's lymph node. All patients were subjected to fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) and underwent various surgical procedures varying from lumpectomy to modified radical mastectomy depending on the result of FNAC. All specimens were subjected to histopathological analyses.

Results: The age of patients varied from 17 to 70 year, most of the malignancies were found between 50 to 70 years of age, positive family history of breast cancer found in 6 patients (2 malignancies), history of breast trauma in 4 patients (no malignancy), time of appearance of the mass varied from 1 to 13 months. All masses were discovered by the patients themselves, onset of menarche varied from 11 to 15 years. Sixty five patients were married (7 malignancies), 10 patients of them had no offspring (2 malignancies), 20 patients used pills irregularly during their reproductive age. Local examination revealed 44 masses in the left breast (7 malignancies), and 36 in the right breast (6 malignancies), 38 masses located in the upper outer quadrant (5 malignancies). The size of the masses varied from 2 to 7 cm, 9 patients had nipple discharge (4 malignancies), 3 patients with remote nipple retraction (no malignancy), 67 masses were mobile (10 malignancies), 10 masses were hard (6 malignancies), 59 were firm (7 malignancies), 11 lesions were soft (1 malignancy), and 10 patients had mobile ipsilateral axillary lymph node(s) (5 malignancies). The FNAC showed 12 cases of malignancies while histopathological examination proved that 13 cases were malignant (one false negative result of FNAC).

Conclusion: It is impossible for the clinical examination to be certain which breast mass is malignant especially in the early stage. In order not to miss malignant breast condition, all breast mass should be taken in suspicious and should subjected to FNAC to determine its nature.

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Keywords: Breast lump, breast malignancy, FNAC

INTRODUCTION

Breast lump is a common problem in women which can occur at any age [1]. Malignant breast disease is considered to be the commonest malignancy that affects female

worldwide, having an incidence of 19 to 24% and mortality of about 20% of cancer death in women [2, 3]. In Iraq, breast was the most common site of cancer accounting for 18% of all cases of cancer with Infiltrating duct carcinoma accounting for 63% of all cases.

Screening programs have adopted for all ladies after the age of 40 or 50 year by many countries as an

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attempt for the early detection of breast malignancy [2].

In Mosul city, mammography as screening tool is still not adopted, and breast self-examination is not performed adequately in most ladies in this locality.

There is no pathognomonic sign or symptom for breast cancer. This is why it is not possible for doctor working without laboratory investigations to know for certain whether the breast lump is benign or malignant on clinical basis alone [5].

This study aimed to light up the effectiveness of clinical examination in evaluating breast lump, as an approach for defining the nature of the lump in comparison with fine needle aspiration cytology (FNAC) using histopathological assessment as the gold standard for evaluation of the effectiveness and comparison.

PATIENTS AND METHODS

A prospective study was carried out at Al-Jamhori Teaching Hospital in Mosul, during four years period from 1st January 2007 to 31st December 2010. All the patients were assessed and managed by one Consultant Surgeon. Initially the study included 92 female patients with breast mass. However, 7 patients on presentation had advanced malignancy in form of malignant ulcer, arm edema, cancer-encirclings; fixed maxillary lymph node, or distal metastases, and other 5 patients refused surgical interference. These 12 patients were excluded from the study, which continued with 80 patients presented only with breast mass.

The clinical history included: age of the patient, duration of the mass, positive family history for breast cancer, history of breast trauma, time of menarche or menopause, menstrual cycle regulation, marital state, number of children, breast feeding and the use of contraceptive pills.

Local breast examination included the evaluation of: the size, site, mobility and consistency of the mass, nipple discharge, nipple retraction, and the state of axillary lymph node.

FNAC was performed to all masses and the results were taken in consideration for planning surgical intervention, in case of suspicious or inadequate FNA result, the test was repeated again after one week and the final result mentioned to be satisfactory. The local complication of FNA was recorded. The specimens were subjected to histopathological evaluation, which was regarded as the final diagnosis to which the clinical finding was compared with.

RESULTS

The age of the patients in relation to the number of breast masses and their histopathological finding is shown in table 1.

Age (year)	Number	Benign	Malignant
17-20	4	4	0
21-30	5	4	1
31-40	10	8	2
41-50	22	20	2
51-60	20	16	4
61-70	16	12	4

Table 1. Relation between number of masses and histopathological finding

The family history of breast cancer in first-degree relative was positive in 6 patients (7.5%), two of them proved to have malignancy. The relation between the marital state to the number of benign and malignant lesion is shown in table 2.

Marital state	Number (%)	Benign	Malignant
single	14 (17.5%)	10 (71.5%)	4 (28.5%)
married, no children	10 (12.5%)	8 (80%)	2 (20%)
married, with children	56 (70%)	44 (78.5%)	7 (12.5%)
total	80 (100%)	67 (83.75%)	13 (16.25%)

Table 2. Relation of marital state to number of benign and malignant lesion

The relation between menstrual state and the histopathology is shown in table 3.

Menstrual state	Number (%)	Benign	Malignant
Pre menopause	30 (37.5)	27 (90%)	3 (10%)
Post menopause	50 (42%)	40 (80%)	10 (20%)

Table 3. Relation between menstrual state and histopathology finding.

The duration between the first observation of the breast mass by the patient and the medical examination (by the author) varied between 1 to 13 months. The reasons for asking medical help were as follows:

1. Psychological upset in 38 patients (47.5%), 4 with malignancy.
2. Rapid growing mass in 18 patients (22.5%), 4 with malignancy.
3. Painful mass in 15 patients (18.75%), 1 with malignancy.
4. Nipple discharge in 9 patients (11.25%), 4 with malignancy.

There were 36 masses in the right breast and 44 in the left one. The site of the mass in relation to the quadrant of breast and their nature are shown on figures 1, 2, 3.

Figure 1

No. of masses in right breast

No. of masses in left breast

Figure 2

No. of benign masses in Rt breast

No. of benign masses in Lt breast

No. of malignant masses
in Rt breast

Figure 3

No. of malignant masses
in Lt breast

The relation between the size of the mass and histopathological finding is shown in table 4.

Size in cm	Number	Benign	Malignant
2	6	5	1
3	13	13	0
4	9	6	3
5	20	15	5
6	23	21	2
7	9	7	2

Table 4. Relation between size of breast mass and histopathological finding

The relation between the mass consistency and histopathological finding is shown in table 5.

Consistency	Number	Benign	Malignant
Firm	59 (73%)	53 (98%)	6 (11%)
Hard	10 (12.5%)	4 (40%)	6 (60%)
Soft	11 (14%)	10 (91%)	1 (9%)
Total	80 (100%)	67 (84.25%)	13 (15.75%)

Table 5. Relation between mass consistency and histopathological finding

The type of discharge in relation to histopathological finding is shown in table 6. (Nipple discharge was positive in 9 patients).

Type of discharge	Number	Benign	Malignant
Blood	5	3	2
Serous	3	2	1
Pus	1	1	0
Total	9	6	3

Table 6. Type of discharge in relation to histopathological finding.

Four masses (5%) showed tethering to skin, only 2 proved to be malignant, the other 2 were antibioma.

Ten patients (12.5%) had mobile ipsilateral axillary lymph node enlargement on clinical bases. FNAC of the related breast masses proved that 6 masses were

State of axillary LN	Number (%)	Benign	Malignant
palpable	10 (12.5%)	6 (60%)	4 (40%)
Not palpable	70 (87.5%)	61 (87%)	9 (13%)

Table 7. Relation between lymph node enlargement and histopathology

malignant with the same result of histopathology study, those with benign lesions and positive axillary lymph node enlargement, 2 patients had antibioma and 4 patients had ductectasia.

Table 7 illustrates the relation between lymph node enlargement and histopathology finding.

The FNAC was done to all patients, 6 cases (7.5%) showed inadequate sampling as recorded by the histopathologist, the test was repeated after 7 days and the second result was documented to be satisfactory and taken in consideration, no patients of them proved to be of malignant condition.

in 14 patients (17%) where analgesia were needed till time of operation, ecchymosed skin happened in 30 patients (37.5%) after FNA, 2 of them with malignancy, this complication doesn't affect the strategy of surgery.

Pain at site of FNA was common, but usually mild and can be tolerated by most patients, it was severe only

Histopathological examination of the excised tissues revealed one false negative result of FNA, table 7.

Type of the disease	By FNAC	By histopathology
Fibro adenoma	45	44
Malignant tumor	12	13
Ductectasia	10	10
Antibioma	6	6
Galactocel	4	4
Phyllods	3	3
Total	80	80

Table 8. Results of FNA and histopathology

DISCUSSION

Breast tissue responds to hormonal changes throughout life especially during reproductive period, therefore a lump may occur at any time and at any age [1].

The presence of a lump does not always indicate malignancy. It may be impossible on clinical bases to know for certain which lump is benign or malignant. This is particularly so in the early stages where each mass may show

itself with different symptoms or signs. For this reason and in order not to miss malignancy, further investigation is needed to prove the diagnosis [4].

More than 80% of breast cancer cases occur in women above 50 years of age [6]. This may be attributed to that increasing age is associated with impaired repair mechanism that makes age a major risk factor for common solid tumor including breast cancer, although no age is immune [6]. In our study, the incidence of malignancy is increasing with age but we have a 23 year old female with malignant breast mass and another 4 malignancies at age of thirties

and forties. Another study [7] showed that 3% of breast mass occurring between 20 to 29 year and 10% between 30 to 39 year of age were malignant in nature. For this reason, any breast mass regardless of the age, must be regarded clinically as possibly malignant till it is proved otherwise by histopathological evaluation [8].

A positive family history of breast malignancy is a document risk factor but no specific pattern of inheritance is evident [9]. In our study, 6 patients (7.5%) had such history, but only 2 of them proved to have malignancy. On the other hand, nullipara woman, early menarche, late menopause and non-breast feeding mother are at greater risk because of prolonged hormonal effect on breast tissue. However, malignancy is commonly found in multipara and breast fed mothers.

Although both breasts can be involved by malignancy, the left side may be affected more, with 50% at the upper outer quadrant, 20% at sub-areolar region and 10% at each remaining quadrants [10]. These figures are more or less similar to our finding; both indicate that breast malignancy can occur at any side and site with predilection at upper outer quadrant which is indeed the common site for benign lumps as well, as proved in this study.

About 70% of malignant breast masses are hard in consistency, and some 30% are of other texture [5]. On the other hand, some benign lesions are hard enough to become impossible to differentiate them from malignancy like fat necroses, chronic mammary mastitis, granular myoblastoma and sclerosing adenoses [5, 11, 12, 13]. This means that the hard consistency of the mass is not a pathognomonic sign for breast malignancy.

Blood nipple discharge in association with breast mass carries a risk of malignancy in 20 to 30% [14], as also shown in our study. Still there is malignant tumor without discharge and a benign lesion with blood discharge.

The clinically palpable axillary lymph node may be valueless and misleading in case of breast lump. This may be due to that, stage 1 malignant tumor has no lymph node involvement, and some palpable lymph node may be due to hyperplasia or infection rather than invasion. Dudley et al [15] cast a debate about the validity of axillary lymph node examination. They asked 5 senior surgeons to examine the axillae of 10

ladies whose breast were covered, 3 of them with normal breast and with no reason expecting the axillary lymph node to be enlarged, 3 patients had breast cancer and 4 patients with breast abscess. There was astonishing lack of agreement between the examiners regarding the finding, which indicates that staging by clinical examination for axillary lymph node is both valueless and misleading.

In this study, 10 patients had palpable axillary lymph node, 4 of them proved to be malignant other 9 patients with malignancy had negative axillary lymph node.

The key stone for diagnosis of breast lump is FNAC, which has a sensitivity of 98% and global efficiency of 93% making it an accurate method for differentiating benign from malignant breast lump¹⁶. Schmann *et al*¹⁷ claimed that, all breast lumps should be excised to avoid risk of undiagnosing malignancy, but we and others^{18,19} prefer that all palpable breast lumps must undergo FNAC first specially if there is no access to a reliable mammography facility [18], which is not always enough to determine the nature of a disease with certainty [19]. The study compared the result of FNAC and histopathology and proved that the result is 99% the same (one false negative result).

FNAC is an effective method of diagnosing carcinoma of the breast and can prevent unnecessary surgery for benign disease in woman of any age without increasing the risk of missing cancer [20]. FNAC has many advantages, it's simple, rapid, relatively painless (that is why it's accepted and tolerated by patient), it does not need local or general anesthesia, inexpensive and reliable method for diagnosis of breast mass. In compare result of FNAC to subsequent histopathological examination [, the false negative results was 2.5%, which is similar to result of other studies whereas the false negative rate between 0 to 4% [21].

In conclusion, it is not wise to depend fully on clinical examination alone to judge whether a breast lump is benign or not, especially in early presentation because there is no pathognomonic sign for malignancy. All physical signs were found in both malignant and benign lesions; therefore FNA is the only answer and should be the rule for further assessment of breast mass at any age, size and consistency.

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The association of methotrexate and 6-mercaptopurin maintenance therapy with hepatotoxic lesion in Leukemic patients

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The maintenance chemotherapy (MT) regimen for patients with acute lymphoblastic leukaemia (ALL) includes the use of combination of daily oral 6-mercaptopurine (6MP) and weekly oral methotrexate (MTX) that continued for 2-2.5 years. 56 children (volunteers) of both sex involved in this study were selected from Baghdad Medical City / AL-Mansour-Pediatric hospital, as follows:-

1. The first group involves 10 patients (5 boys and 5 girls) with ALL who were newly diagnosed and selected just prior to start with treatment protocol; median age, 5.8 years. This group of patients was considered to be the baseline group for this study.

2. The second group involves 30 patients with ALL (19 boys and 11 girls) receiving the above mentioned maintenance therapy; median age, 8.6 years; with duration of therapy ranged between 5-36 months which were divided according to that duration into 4 subgroups as follows:

3. A group of 16 healthy children (9 boys and 7 girls) was selected; median age, 8.4 years. This group was considered to be the control for this study.

Laboratory analysis of liver function tests were made for the above three groups include; serum alkaline phosphatase activity (ALP); serum Alanin Transaminase (SGPT), Aspartate transaminases activities (SGOT); serum gamma-glutamyl transferase activity (GGT); serum albumin level (ALB); total serum protein level (T.S.P); and total serum bilirubin level (T.S.B).

There was no significant difference between the levels of liver function tests analysis for control and baseline subjects .

With respect to the selected 30 patients with ALL under maintenance therapy (MT) , the total serum protein and serum albumin levels were within the normal reference range. 7 of them with different treatment durations, were showed abnormally high levels of liver function tests (serum GOT, GPT, GGT, ALP, and T.S.B), which were found to be higher than the normal reference range for each one, these results are illustrated in the table below:

Pharmacist.DPL

Iraqi Ministry of Health

Patient s	Sex	Age (Years)	Duration of MT (months)	T	GO U/L	GPT U/L	T.S. mg/ dl	GGT U/L	ALP K.K.U/dl
1	M	4	5		23	57	1.6	40	23
2	M	9	5		19	35	1.5	42	28
3	M	1	10.8		100	75	1.3	38	22
4	M	2	6		230	100	3.3	78.9	40
5	M	5	22		113	150	1.4	45.5	23
6	F	3	1		100	110	2.5	69.4	29
7	M	1.4	9		190	130	1.8	63	26

A comparison between the mean values of the liver function tests parameters (S.GOT, S.GPT, S.GGT, S.ALP) of 4 patients groups and the control subjects group, are expressed in figures (1-4).

Figure-1: Serum GOT concentration (U/L) for control subjects and patients with ALL under maintenance therapy with 6-mercaptopurine and methotrexate combination.

Figure-2 Serum GPT concentration (U/L) for control subjects and patients with ALL under maintenance therapy with 6-mercaptopurine and methotrexate combination.

Figure - 3: Serum GGT concentration (U/L) for control subjects and patients with ALL under maintenance therapy with 6-mercaptopurine and methotrexate combination.

Figure-4: Serum alkaline phosphatase concentration (K.K.U/dl) for control subjects and patients with ALL under maintenance therapy with 6-mercaptopurine and methotrexate combination.

With respect to the selected 30 ALL patients under MT it was found that:

1. Serum total protein and albumin levels were normal compared to those of the control subjects. This is mainly due to the ability of the liver to increase protein output approximately two-fold during diseases associated with protein loss^[1].

2. Serum GOT, GPT, ALP, and GGT enzymes and total serum bilirubin levels.

7 of the selected 30 patients with ALL under MT at different treatment durations have abnormally elevated serum levels of the above parameters higher than those of the control subjects. GPT present usually in the cytoplasm of the liver cell while GOT has both cytoplasmic and mitochondrial isoenzymes, So in patients who have serum GPT higher than GOT level, this mean that only the cytoplasmic form of

GOT is released into the circulation from reversibly damaged parenchymal cells and this is mostly associated with mild degree of liver tissue injury⁽²⁾. While in patients who have serum GOT higher than GPT level, this mean that both cytoplasmic and mitochondrial forms of GOT are released, and this is mostly occur in chronic or severe hepatocellular damage like in cirrhosis^[3]. However, the exact detection of the type of chronic lesion induced by chemotherapy wheather its fibrosis or cirrhosis, could be made by liver biopsy.

The rise in ALP, GGT enzymes and total serum bilirubin levels is considered to be an indicator for presence of cholestatic lesion mainly intrahepatic cholestasis, because its frequently associated with liver cell destruction^[3], and its known to be the hepatotoxic lesion induced by the long-term use of

6MP in treatment of childhood ALL⁽²⁾. Both ALP, GGT are membrane associated enzymes which anchored to the membrane of liver cells particularly to the biliary canaliculus; they tend to be released in only small amounts following hepatocellular damage, but in much greater amounts when there is cholestasis⁽³⁾. However, serum GGT activity provides more sensitive index of cholestasis than ALP and has the advantage of being more liver specific⁽⁴⁾.

For the remaining 23 ALL patients under MT Serum GOT, GPT levels were abnormally higher than those of the control subjects. The presence of some of these 23 patients with normal levels of some of the liver biochemical tests used in this study, and some others with abnormally higher levels, compared to those of the control subjects, may be due to the presence of inter-individual variation in the pharmacokinetics of oral 6MP and MTX, and the degree of hepatotoxicity induced by any of these two drugs may reflect the magnitude of systemic drug exposure⁽⁵⁾. Another important factor is the drug compliance, which cannot be excluded as a possible contributing factor⁽⁶⁾.

Conclusion

1. There was no hepatocellular damage or injury induced by ALL alone.
2. The long-term use of MTX (20 mg/m²/week) and 6MP (75 mg/m²/day) during the maintenance therapy for childhood ALL may lead to the development of hepatocellular damage or destruction mainly induced by MTX, and intrahepatic cholestasis that induced by 6MP.
3. 7 of 30 selected patients with ALL (23%) under the above mentioned combination at different treatment durations were highly affected by these two agents and showed abnormally elevated serum enzymes GOT, GPT ALP, GGT, and total serum bilirubin levels, they have both hepatocellular destruction and intrahepatic cholestasis, and they may be suspected to have even liver fibrosis or cirrhosis, due to the hepatotoxicity of MTX, this could be detected using liver biopsy examination.
4. Liver biochemical changes during MT provide insensitive reflections of MTX-induced hepatic injury, and liver biopsy is the only accurate technique to assess MTX-induced hepatotoxic lesion

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Avulsion fracture around the knee associated with forceful manipulation by bonesetter

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Abstract

Background: The care of fracture patients in the developing countries is substandard compared to the developed countries. Bonesetters, for example, have become understandably popular. In this paper, we report and discuss a case to highlight this practice in Iraq in order to improve the standard.

Case report: A 51 year old lady had her left knee forcefully manipulated by a bonesetter. As a result, she sustained an avulsion fracture of the femoral epicondyle requiring plaster immobilization.

Conclusion: The current standard is poor and no regulation for the practice of bonesetter exists. The health system has to study the options required to deal with this issue and improve it.

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Keywords: bonesetter, fracture, knee, health, regulations

Introduction

A bonesetter is a practitioner of joint manipulation. Before the advent of chiropractors, osteopaths and physical therapists, bonesetters were the main providers

of this type of treatment in the world [1, 2, 3]. Bonesetters would also reduce joint dislocations and 're-set' bone fractures.

The original spinal adjustment was a variation of a procedure known today as spinal manipulation. This form of treatment has documented use as far back as Hippocrates, the ancient Egyptians and Asian cultures and was carried through the ages by families of bonesetters. The modern form of spinal manipulation techniques have characteristic biomechanical features, and are usually associated with an audible "popping" sound.

The garotte was given to the bonesetters and physicians in the French and European Revolution. Five thousand two hundred bonesetters were garotted at the same time as well as four thousand eight hundred physicians, as both were political naive middle class

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crafts. Other "Lay" bonesetters continued to practice in some parts of the world to this date [2,3].

The current case is reported to highlight the bonesetters' practice in Iraq in order to improve the standard.

Case report

A 51 year old female with mild osteo-arthritis of the left knee attended a bonesetter seeking treatment. The bonesetter, forcefully manipulated the knee in different directions including in valgus and varus direction. The patient experienced sudden sharp pain during the procedure, and felt a crack. She was unable to put weight on the leg following this, and attended the fracture clinic in Azadi Hospital, Kirkuk, Iraq. The knee was swollen and tender on mobilization. The range of knee movement was 20-60°. Radiographs of the knee revealed an avulsion fracture of the lateral femoral epicondyle with comminution.

The case was treated with long leg cylinder for 2 months and she was allowed knee movement following this. 3 months following injury, the range of knee movement became 0-90°, but continued to have pain.

Fig 1: Lateral epicondyle fracture caused by forceful manipulation

Discussion

Femoral fracture following manipulation by bonesetter is not reported in English literature. The only case reports written up are manipulation of stiff knees following knee replacement [4].

The number of bonesetters seems to have increased over the last few years in Iraq. It is unclear what sort of training the bonesetters have, and there are no regulations controlling their practice. This raises concerns. The questions to raise are: why do the patients go to the bonesetters, and why are there no regulations controlling them. It is evident that the health system in Iraq struggles with lack of facilities

and expertise in the hospitals and poor hospital management. Furthermore, there is also the issue of poor health education and ignorance on the patient side. It is therefore vital that all these issues are dealt with at the same time.

The middle Ages development of bonesetters was within a body well-regulated in the form of the bonesetters guild. This guild served as a means of training, disciplining, adjudicating and mastering its craft. The bonesetters guild records were held in Austria and surrounding towns, and was generally opposite the physicians guild, due to their closeness in cooperation. Napoleon in 1802 sacked their respective guilds and persecuted their members until 1806. The mainstay of the craft was seven-year apprenticeships by boys 12-17 who lived within guild huts and travelled with master craftsmen to spend time with various teachers. It derived its training from the Roman and Greek "skeleton men" and the ancient Egyptian "men of the hands". They entered university training along with physicians four hundred years before medical practitioners then known as allopaths. The guilds' models were adopted but Americanized by chiropractic. The bonesetters guild was present at the foundation year of the University of Notre Dame Bonesetters practice in the United Kingdom and some are listed with a voluntary register set up as a limited company called Unified Bonesetters Ltd. As no legislation has been passed to regulate bonesetters, the title of Bonesetter is not protected [2,3]. It is surprising that such a regulation does not seem to be existing or practiced at this era in many developing countries.

In the developing countries, the surgeon faces many challenges in the endeavour to obtain best outcome. This is of multitude aetiology. Lack of training and poor budget is some of these factors that undermine the good outcome of treatment of fractures (3). These may be some of the reasons why patients seek treatment from bonesetter.

CONCLUSION

The current case is brought as an example to highlight this very important health regulation issue. The complications arising because of the lack of control of this practice are grievous and serious. I suggest that the department of health sets up committees to investigate this and set up regulations. The hospital standards have to improve at the same time.

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Severe upper gastrointestinal bleeding in a healthy full term neonate

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Abstract

A healthy full-term neonate developed massive upper gastrointestinal bleeding at the third day of life. The pregnancy and delivery have been uneventful. He was shown to have multiple gastro-esophageal ulceration by endoscopy and biopsy. The patient responded to conservative treatment.

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Keywords: Upper gastrointestinal bleeding, Neonate, Peptic ulcer, Endoscopy

Introduction

The occurrence of profuse upper gastrointestinal bleeding in the neonatal period of life, mainly in preterm babies or in full term neonates treated in intensive care units, is relatively uncommon during the neonatal period.¹⁻³ In such patients, peptic ulcers are usually classified as secondary stress ulcers, and are associated with other serious conditions, such as intracerebral bleeding, raised intracranial pressure, asphyxia, respiratory

failure, hypoglycemia, sepsis or prolonged use of drugs such as corticosteroids, indomethacin and tolazoline.^{1,3,4} Even more unusual is the occurrence of significant upper gastro-intestinal bleeding in healthy full-term infants.⁴

I report a case of severe upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage at the third day of life in an apparently healthy full-term newborn, without any clear predisposing factors.

Case Report

A 3.5-kg full-term male, Jordanian newborn of 40 weeks gestational age was delivered by spontaneous normal vaginal delivery, after an uneventful pregnancy and labor. The mother was a 25 years old primigravida, non-smoker, who had no history of medical illness, and not taken any medications such as aspirin during pregnancy and labor. There was no family history of peptic ulcer or

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hematological diseases. The delivery was normal and the APGAR score at one and five minutes was 9 and 10 respectively. No suction or resuscitation was required at birth. There was no vomiting in the first forty-eight hours.

At his third day of life he vomited fresh blood, for which he was admitted to Prince Ali Hospital. A large bore naso-gastric tube was inserted, and 20 ml of fresh blood was aspirated from the stomach. The Apt alkali denaturation test on the gastric aspirate was positive for fetal blood and excluded swallowed maternal blood.

The newborn was well, active, and not septic. The pulse rate was 150 per minute and good volume, respiratory rate 35 per minute and blood pressure 60/40 mmHg. He was slightly jaundiced and had good sucking and Moro reflexes. Full examination of all systems was entirely normal.

Gastric lavage showed further fresh blood. He was commenced on intravenous fluids and kept fasting.

Initial results were packed cell volume 48%, white cell count 13,000/mm³ with normal differential count, platelet count 263,000/mm³, reticulocyte count 3% and normal blood film, serum electrolytes, kidney and liver function.

Prothrombin time and partial thromboplastin time were 13/13, and 40/36 respectively. Fibrinogen level was not taken. Stool hem-occult was positive and a plain abdomen X-ray was normal.

The baby was given 40 ml of fresh whole blood because the PCV dropped to 39% after two hours and then to 32% after six hours. The baby continued to pass fresh blood from the stomach and then a melanotic stool was passed. Another 40 ml of blood was transfused.

Endoscopy showed multiple gastroesophageal ulcers at the lower esophagus and in the stomach body. Some blood was noted around the margins of ulcers but there was no evidence of a visible or active bleeding. A biopsy was taken and showed ulcerations with severe neutrophilic infiltrate of mucosa and submucosa with no bacterial or viral inclusions, or fungal organisms (Figure). Bacteriological culture was negative. Bleeding stopped spontaneously and during the next 48 hours, his vital signs and PCV remained stable.

The baby was commenced on cimetidine 5mg/kg every 8 hours and there was no further bleeding. He was breast-fed after two days and discharged from the hospital after one week. He was treated with oral cimetidine 15mg/kg day for eight weeks.

He had no further hematemesis. His packed cell volume was stable and endoscopy was not repeated. He used to be followed in the clinic. He is now five years healthy child with normal growth and development. Informed consent to publish this information was granted from the patient's family.

Figure: Biopsy specimen showing mucosal ulceration with neutrophilic infiltrate of mucosa and submucosa.

DISCUSSION

Ulcer disease uncommon in children and is very rare in the newborn. It is classified as primary or secondary and is caused by factors that affect the integrity of the intestinal mucosa.¹⁻⁶

A number of factors are important in the development of primary ulcer disease including gastric acidity, blood group O and high serum levels of pepsinogen. A family history is noted in 25-50% of children with duodenal ulcers and concordance for duodenal ulcer is 50% for monozygotic twins. Other factors that appear to be important are cigarette smoking, climate conditions, dietary habits (alcohol consumption), and emotional strain in the mother.^{1,2} Also *Helicobacter pylori* is an important factor in

childhood gastritis and chronic peptic ulcer disease.^{7,8} Secondary ulcer or stress ulcer accounts for 80% of peptic ulcer disease during infancy and is associated with shock, respiratory failure, sepsis, hypoglycemia, burns, intracranial lesions and the use of aspirin and other non-steroidal anti-inflammatory agents that compromise prostaglandin synthesis and mucosal defense.^{1,3,4}

The incidence of primary peptic ulcer in childhood is unknown since not all patients undergo radiological or endoscopic evaluation, and some heal spontaneously before a diagnosis is made.²

Studies on peptic ulcer disease were performed on children rather than newborns. Prior to the development of fiberoptic endoscopy, surgeons reported cases of neonates who developed massive upper gastrointestinal bleeding and or perforation due to acute peptic ulcer in the first week of life.⁹⁻¹³ The first case of fatal bleeding from gastric ulceration's during the first day of life was reported in 1941.⁹ There was a strong association between the presence of bleeding and stressful conditions affecting the mother.

There are few previous reports of full-term healthy newborns with profuse upper gastrointestinal hemorrhage in the first week of life.⁶ In 1978 Liebman et al.¹⁴ reported the first case of massive upper gastrointestinal bleeding in the newborn to be diagnosed by fiberoptic endoscopy which showed multiple superficial erosions of the greater curvature of the stomach. This case illustrated the usefulness of fiberoptic endoscopy, which was being introduced at that time. In 1983, Dunn et al.¹⁵ reported 39 children with peptic ulcer disease, 34 of them had secondary ulcers. Twenty-seven presented with hemorrhage and 12 with perforation. All were managed successfully and there were no recurrences.

It is not clear why healthy full-term newborns with no perinatal complications develop peptic ulcer in the first few days of life. A study of four cases of healthy full-term newborns with massive upper gastrointestinal bleeding in the first 48 hours of life, showed one with a positive family history of peptic ulcer disease.⁶ A positive family history was reported in 20-63% of older children with chronic ulcers.² In our case family history of peptic ulcer disease was negative. Tudor¹⁰ reported a 20% positive family history of peptic ulcer disease and Deckelbaum et al. a history in all cases of primary gastric ulcer.

In adults hyper pepsinogenemia is a reliable marker of the genetic predisposition to duodenal ulcer. In infants only half had increased pepsinogen and they came from families with hyper pepsinogenemic parents.^{17,18} We did not measure pepsinogen levels in neither our case nor his parents.

The acid secretory apparatus of the oxyntic glands develops early during the second trimester of gestation, suggesting that the fetus have the capacity for acid secretion during the second half of fetal life¹⁸. Gastric acid output normally increases dramatically during the first hours of life. This may be related to an increased parietal cell area mass per unit area of the stomach in the newborn infant. Whether a surge of gastric acid secretion in the immediate perinatal period is responsible for neonatal peptic ulceration is not known.¹⁹⁻²¹

It was noticed that secondary ulcers caused by CNS disorders are frequently associated with hyperacidity, and hypergastrinemia.¹⁵ The hypothesis that increased maternal stress during the third trimester leads to high circulating levels of maternal gastrin, and mandate the development of hypertrophic pyloric stenosis or peptic ulcer disease remain controversial.⁶ In our case there was no evidence that maternal gastrin level played a role in the development of ulcer.

In all newborns reported to have upper gastrointestinal bleeding, including our case, the bleeding has been severe that mandate blood transfusion. Naso-gastric aspirate may not accurately predict the cessation of bleeding in patients with duodenal ulcers, and only endoscopy can localize the source of bleeding and determine whether endoscopic sclerotherapy or thermocoagulation is necessary.⁶

In healthy newborns the bleeding can be managed conservatively. It is not clear whether tagamet plays a role in the resolution of the bleeding, but it is usually recommended because of the increase in the gastric acid secretion in the immediate perinatal period.⁶ If bleeding ulcer develops complications, such as perforation or uncontrolled bleeding, surgical management is required.¹⁵ Healing of the ulcers should be documented by endoscopy before discontinuing H2 receptor antagonist treatment, although some authors suggest that a second endoscopic procedure is not necessary provided that the infant is clinically well.⁴ In our case the newborn dramatically improved on cimetidine treatment, and therefore a second endoscopy was not performed. Our patient is now five years old, healthy, and developing normally. The long-term prognosis for these patients is unknown.

Conclusion

Gastro-esophageal ulcer disease is very rare in healthy full-term newborns. It is usually severe enough to need urgent medical intervention, and can be fatal if perforation occurs. The long-term prognosis is not known, although no recurrences have been reported and it is not a risk factor for peptic ulcer disease in the childhood.

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